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Correcting for Multiple Testing in Change Point Detection of Global Vegetation Trends

MASTER'S THESIS M.SC. GEOINFORMATICS

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The Cover page was designed by my dear friend Pauline Delphin (@pauline_delphin). She produced this impression of my thesis based on keywords and the experiences I shared with her throughout my work.

As most of my friends do not study or work in my field, my work sometimes felt even more specialized and niched, leaving me somewhat isolated. This different perspective on my work and Pauline's and my shared passion for performing arts and design makes me feel more connected.

Abstract

BACKGROUND: Global Vegetation studies are mainly focused on monotonic trend detection and have resulted in the image of a greening world. Monotonic trend analysis may omit subtrends and changes in trend direction, whereas a change point detection can capture such breaks. A testing procedure is commonly applied at the grid cell level of satellite images, which leads to the multiple testing problem. Multiple testing can increase the probability of false positive results, even more if data is spatially autocorrelated.

METHODS: We have performed a change point detection with Modified Cumulative Sums of Residuals Test (MCUSUM) on a global 37-year Leaf Area Index (LAI) record, applying an adjusted version of the permutation-based multiple testing correction by Cortés et al. (2020) for robust inference.

RESULTS: The MCUSUM performed rather conservatively, showing considerably fewer significant change point pixels than other global vegetation studies. On the global scale, in line with other studies, greening types prevailed, reversal types were less frequent, however. Thus, we gathered no sustained evidence for an increase in global browning trends. Our change point timing estimates showed high coincidence with satellite platform changes, challenging their reliability. The multiple testing correction is easily transferable to a new use case. Yet, the testing method should have a reasonably short computing time to make the permutation technically feasible. Our adjusted version detected smaller significant clusters than the original one.

CONCLUSION: We propose the permutation-based multiple testing correction for use with gridded environmental data and hope to further increase awareness of the multiple testing problem in the remote sensing community.

Zusammenfassung

HINTERGRUND: Viele Studien zur Veränderung globaler Vegetationsbedeckung kamen zu dem Schluss, dass die Welt in den letzten Jahrzehnten grüner geworden ist, d.h. die Menge an Vegetation zugenommen hat. Die meisten Arbeiten stützen sich dabei auf monotone Trendanalysen. Damit werden Unterprozesse vereinfacht und Perioden gleichbleibender Produktivität oder eine mögliche Trendumkehr innerhalb des Untersuchungszeitraums nicht berücksichtigt. Solche Strukturbrüche können mit geeigneten Methoden erkannt werden und liefern dabei mehr Details als eine herkömmliche Trendanalyse. Satellitenbilder sind die wichtigste Datenquelle für großräumige Vegetationsanalysen. Dabei wird üblicherweise jedes einzelne Pixel einer Satellitenbild-Zeitreihe auf Strukturbrüche getestet, was tausende Hypothesen-Tests ergibt. Dieses Vorgehen erhöht die Wahrscheinlichkeit, falsch positive Testergebnisse zu erhalten und daraus falsche Erkenntnisse abzuleiten - das Problem des multiplen Testens.

METHODEN: In dieser Arbeit wurde eine 37-Jahre-Satellitenbild-Zeitreihe eines Blattflächenindex mit dem Modified Cumulative Sums of Residuals Test (MCUSUM) auf Strukturbrüche hin untersucht und eine permutations-basierte Korrekturmethode von Cortés et al. (2020) für multiples Testen angewandt, um statistisch verlässliche Ergebnisse zu erzielen.

ERGEBNISSE: Im Vergleich zu anderen Studien konnten wir mit MCUSUM global deutlich weniger Pixel mit Strukturbrüchen identifizieren. Ähnlich wie in anderen Studien überwogen Pixel, die einen Zuwachs an Vegetation darstellten, jedoch waren Pixel mit einer Trendumkehr deutlich seltener. Viele der ermittelten Strukturbrüche fanden im gleichen Jahr statt wie der Wechsel der Satellitenplattformen, was an der Zuverlässigkeit der Schätzungen zweifeln lässt. Die Korrekturmethode von Cortés et al. (2020) konnte leicht auf einen neuen Anwendungsfall übertragen werden und die Anpassungen ermöglichte es, noch kleinere signifikante Cluster zu entdecken als mit der ursprünglichen Version. Der verwendete Test sollte jedoch eine möglichst geringe Rechenzeit aufweisen, da die Prozedur sonst sehr aufwendig wird.

SCHLUSSFOLGERUNG: Die Korrekturmethode kann gute Ergebnisse erzielen und ist für Umweltdaten mit Gitterstruktur zu empfehlen. Diese Studie leistet hoffentlich einen Beitrag dazu, dass dem Problem des multiplen Testens in der Fernerkundung künftig mehr Beachtung geschenkt wird.

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Symbols

$x_{1:n}$	Observations of an ordered Data Dequence
t	Time Steps of a Time Series
T	Length of a Time Series
F	A Probability Distribution Function
m	Number of Change Points
τ	Location of a Change Point
$C(\cdot)$	Cost Function for Multiple Change Point Detection
λ	Hyperparameter for Multiple Change Point Detection
$\mathbb{P}(m)$	Penalty for Number of Change Points in Multiple Change Point Detection
H_0	Null Hypothesis
H_1	Alternative Hypothesis
α	Alpha Level of a Hypothesis Test
K	Number of simulteanous Tests in a Multiple Testing Setting
$\max T$	Maximum Statistic
u	Significance Threshold in Maximum Statistic Permutation Correction
T_i	Test Statistic for Hypothesis i
W_i^T	Tippet Combining Function for cluster i
\mathcal{P}_i^m	Corrected p-value for Peak Intensity of cluster i
\mathcal{P}_i^s	Corrected p-value for Size of Cluster i
Y_t	Response Variable of a linear Regression
X_t	Regressor Matrix of a linear Regression
β_i	Vector of linear Regression Coefficients
ϵ_t	Residuals of a linear Regression
v_t	Residuals of an autoregressive Model
M_t	Test Statistic of MCUSUM
B	Total Number of Bootstrap Repetitions

Abbreviations

AR(x)	Autoregressive Model of Order x
AVHRR	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer
BFAST	Breaks For Additive Season and Trend
BH	Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) correction
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
BU GIMMS3g	Boston University GIMMS3g LAI
CDR	Climate Data Record
FDR	False Discovery Rate
FWER	Familywise Error Rate
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GIMMS3g	Global Inventory Modeling and Mapping Studies 3rd Generation
GLASS	Global LAnd Surface Satellite
GLOBMAP	Long-term Global Mapping
GTOS	Global Terrestrial Observing System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LTDR	Land Long Term Data Record
MCUSUM	Modified Cumulative Sums of Residuals Test
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration of the United States of America
OLS	Ordinary least squares
RSS	Residual Sum of Squares
STCS	Suprathreshold Cluster Size
TCF	Tippet Combining Function

Chapter 1

Introduction

Vegetation is a crucial part of the terrestrial biosphere and plays a key role in biophysical interactions between land and atmosphere. Different land cover and land use types possess different characteristics that influence the hydrological cycle and surface temperature through absorption and emission of radiation. Thereby they affect the climate from a local to a global scale. Land cover and land use are altered by land management (e.g. deforestation, crop production) as well as natural processes (e.g. climatic variations, weather extremes). Global climate change has led to shifts in climate zones and changes in location, range sizes, and abundance of plant species over the last decades, which likely produce changes in the distribution of biomes and in ecosystem productivity (IPCC, 2019; Lucht et al., 2006; Piao et al., 2019). Changes can be a result of global climate change, however, a rise in vegetation cover might also mitigate processes like increasing land surface temperatures or serve as a land carbon sink (Chen et al., 2019b; Ballantyne et al., 2012). It is necessary to assess these processes and dependencies within the earth system to develop appropriate land management strategies and to improve modeling and projection of interactions, which still exhibit various uncertainties.

The first step towards understanding the mechanisms of vegetation status change and identifying driving forces is to detect and characterize the changes. This includes determining the amount, as well as localization and spatial extent, of greening and browning throughout the globe. Greening and browning are defined as statistically significant trends, positive and negative respectively, in photosynthetic activity and vegetation amount (IPCC, 2019; Chen et al., 2019a).

Satellite sensors are a valuable source of consistent data with high spatial and temporal resolution and have been available for three to four decades now. Remotely sensed indices

such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) or Leaf Area Index (LAI) are used as estimates of photosynthetic activity and vegetation amount. Trends in those measures can therefore be seen as a proxy for processes of greening and browning (Forkel et al., 2013; De Jong et al., 2013; Verbesselt et al., 2010). Many studies agree on an overall greening of the earth in the last decades (IPCC, 2019; De Jong et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2019a; Fensholt et al., 2012; Pan et al., 2018). This has been explained by direct forces like human land use management and indirect forces like CO₂ fertilization and an extended growing season as a result of climate change (Chen et al., 2019a; Fensholt et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2016). Browning, i.e. a decrease in vegetation photosynthetic activity, has as well been detected, although to a much lower global extent - roughly 4% of the global vegetated area vs. 35% of greening. Browning is widely attributed to enhanced drought stress (Pan et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2016; IPCC, 2019).

Studies that look at shorter time spans or allow for changes in trends within the last 30-40 years, however, show a more ambiguous outcome. In some regions, browning rates and extents have exceeded those of greening in the last 20 years. Besides, trend shifts from greening to browning were observed (De Jong et al., 2012; Pan et al., 2018). This indicates, that looking at monotonic long-term trends might omit changes in trends or trends occurring solely in shorter time spans, especially as available time series grow longer and climate change and other human impacts become more apparent (De Jong et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2019; Higginbottom and Symeonakis, 2020; Forkel et al., 2013). Such changes in NDVI or LAI, so-called change points, can be abrupt or gradual. Abrupt changes are caused by disturbances like fires, floods, or diseases. Gradual changes arise over longer time spans and can be attributed to land degradation or changes in climate such as yearly rainfall, atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, or temperature (De Jong et al., 2013; Verbesselt et al., 2010).

In the study of remote sensing vegetation products, statistical analysis is conducted at the pixel level. Depending on the size of the study area and the data used, images have thousands to over a million of grid cells, thus the chosen method is applied this many times. If the method involves a hypothesis test, the probability of false positive results, i.e. erroneously significant results, increases with the number of tests performed on subsamples of the dataset. This is commonly referred to as the multiple comparison or multiple testing problem. If not accounted for, uncontrolled false positive test results are incurred, which may lead to false scientific findings. Cortés et al. (2021) have shown that not correcting for multiple testing can result in an overestimation of global greening trends. They detected greening in only 15% of the terrestrial land surface as opposed to 35% without

correction. In other research fields like neuroimaging, the multiple testing problem is a widely acknowledged issue and several correction procedures have been developed. In the remote sensing community, the problem is rarely considered, although spatial autocorrelation, common in environmental data, might even intensify the problem as clusters of false positive results can arise (Heumann, 2015; Cortés et al., 2020).

Cortés et al. (2020, 2021) have introduced a permutation-based maximum statistic correction method to remote sensing. They use a cluster-based approach in significance testing to tackle the multiple testing problem and possible spatial autocorrelation in gridded environmental data. The aim of the present study is to investigate the applicability and usefulness of the tool for other environmental use cases. Their approach was applied to a change point detection in global vegetation time series data. Furthermore, the results were compared to other change point detection studies to assess the effects of the correction. Although ecological backgrounds and plausibility of the resulting change points will be discussed, this work does not provide an in-depth ecological interpretation and has a rather methodological focus. A detailed outline of the research questions is given in chapter 3.

Content Before the specific methods used in the analysis are presented, a thorough overview of the concepts involved is given. In section 2.1 different change point detection methods and their characteristics, as well as their applications in the environmental sciences are presented. Moreover, methods and results of remote sensing based studies on change point detection in global vegetation trends are reviewed. In section 2.2 the multiple testing problem is explained in depth and different correction approaches are shown with a focus on permutation-based maximum statistic methods. Furthermore the integration of multiple testing correction into environmental analyses is discussed. Based on the theoretical background the research design and specific research questions will be presented in chapter 3. Chapter 4 provides details on the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) 37-year LAI data record and the methods chosen to perform the analysis. This includes data pre-processing, adjustments to the correction procedure by Cortés et al. (2020), the Modified Cumulative Sums of Residuals Test (MCUSUM) for change point detection, and a classification of break points. In chapter 5 the results based on the research questions are presented and thoroughly discussed in chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background

2.1 Change Point Detection

Change points or breakpoints¹ are moments of abrupt change in the behaviour of a time series or data sequence². They might indicate an alteration of the data generating process caused by external events and/or internal systematic changes (Aminikhanghahi and Cook, 2016; van den Burg and Williams, 2020). Unlike trend detection, change point detection does not look for gradual monotonic change along the whole time series but aims to partition the data into segments of different structures or distributions. Yet the individual segments can exhibit trends of different magnitude and direction within their time range.

Change point detection has been a research question for decades in both statistical and non-statistical fields. The first studies on change point detection date back to the 1950s (Page, 1955, 1957) and since then, a vast variety of change point detection methods has been developed and applied in disciplines ranging from finance, engineering, biosciences and linguistic to environmental sciences. It is used to sequence genomic data (Polushina and Sofronov, 2011), to monitor network traffic and detect possible cyber attacks (Kurt et al., 2018), for tracking changes in stock orders and prices (Liu et al., 2008) or to reveal changes in environmental variables like carbon dioxide values in Antarctic ice cores (Banesh et al., 2019) or precipitation and temperature time series (Zarenistanak et al., 2014).

Single Change Point A basic approach to the change point detection problem with *maximum one* change point can be formulated as a generic hypothesis test (Gurevich and

¹The terms breakpoint and change point are used interchangeably.

²Change point detection can be applied to any ordered data also for example genome sequences. However, time series analysis is the most prevalent use case. Therefore the following use of the term *time series* does not imply that methods cannot be used for non-temporal sequences.

Vexler, 2010; Pettitt, 1979; Niu et al., 2016). For $x_{1:n} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ being the observations for time steps $t = 1, 2, \dots, n$, a segment of the time series from $t = a, a + 1, \dots, b$ can be denoted as $x_{a:b}$. Let F_0, F_1, F_2 be three probability distribution functions, the following hypotheses are set:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : x_{1:n} &\sim F_0 && \text{versus} \\ H_1 : x_{1:\tau-1} &\sim F_1, x_{\tau:n} &\sim F_2 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

We test "no change" against the alternative hypothesis of one unknown change point at location τ . The change point denotes the first point of the new segment. Depending on the assumptions made on the distribution functions F_0, F_1 and F_3 , the problem can be studied in a parametric or non-parametric way. A classification scheme for change point detection methods including such assumptions will be given in the following section.

Multiple Change Points Extending the analysis to *multiple* breakpoints, the problem can be formulated as an optimization problem (Killick et al., 2012; van den Burg and Williams, 2020; Truong et al., 2018). There are m ordered change points $\tau_0, \tau_1, \dots, \tau_m$ and the locations $\tau_0 = 1$ and $\tau_{m+1} = n + 1$ are set as convention. The time series will be split into m segments, where the i th segment contains $y_{\tau_{i-1}:\tau_i-1}$. A common approach to identify multiple change points is to minimize

$$\sum_{i=1}^{m+1} [C(y_{\tau_{i-1}:\tau_i-1})] + \lambda \mathbb{P}(m) \tag{2.2}$$

Here $C(\cdot)$ is a cost function for one segment, $\lambda \geq 0$ is a hyperparameter and $\mathbb{P}(m)$ a penalty on the number of breakpoints to avoid overfitting. Aimed at detecting multiple breakpoints, this optimization strategy can still return a single breakpoint if it is the optimal solution.

2.1.1 Overview of Different Methods

The theoretical frameworks 2.1 and 2.2 to address the change point problem are directed towards *offline* change point detection. *Offline* change point detection operates retrospectively using all available data as one batch, whereas *online* approaches incorporate each new data point as it becomes available, aiming to detect a breakpoint as soon as possible after it occurred (Truong et al., 2018; Aminikhanghahi and Cook, 2016). Online methods can facilitate (near) real-time disturbance monitoring and be integrated into early warning/alert systems. Change point detection methods can further be differentiated by

their underlying concept of statistical inference: *frequentist* vs. *bayesian* approaches. A thorough explanation of these basic statistical ideas is beyond the scope of this study. Furthermore, the vast body of research on change point detection in the last decades makes an exhaustive summary of all existing approaches unfeasible. Thus, the concepts discussed here are confined to *frequentist offline* change point detection (see Figure 2.2). Supervised classification methods are not included either, as ground truth data is rarely available in the common applications of change point detection. For online approaches the interested reader is referred to Basseville and Nikiforov (1993), examples of bayesian change point detection are Adams and MacKay (2007); Kurt et al. (2018); Li and Lund (2015) and Aminikhanghahi and Cook (2016) present supervised methods.

Depending on the data and its generating processes, it may be desired to detect a single breakpoint, multiple breakpoints or to assess whether any change exists in the time series regardless of the number of breakpoints. The types of change at breakpoints can vary in nature and different methods are targeted towards detecting certain types of changes. Change points can, for example, reflect a change in mean, variance or in the coefficients of a linear regression (see Figure 2.1). Revisiting the hypothesis testing framework in 2.1, the problem can be addressed in a parametric setting, where the probability distribution functions have known forms that contain certain unknown parameters, hence, changes in those parameters can be monitored. In a non-parametric setting, the distribution functions are assumed to be completely unknown, so in order to detect breakpoints an alternative measure is needed that reflects the data's (in)homogeneity (Gurevich and Vexler, 2010; Truong et al., 2018). A third branch that can but must not involve distributional assumptions are approaches based on linear regression (Militino et al., 2020). Figure 2.1 illustrates a possible classification of change point detection method based on the mentioned criteria and includes examples for the different types. For further reviews and other categorization schemes see Truong et al. (2018); Lee (2010); Aminikhanghahi and Cook (2016); Beaulieu et al. (2012).

Parametric Change Point Detection Assuming a normal distribution, parametric breakpoint methods aim to detect changes in the mean, the variance or both. Several methods use maximum likelihood to compare different segmentations of the time series (Hinkley, 1970; Jen and Gupta, 1987; Horvath, 1993). An alternative is an informational approach based on information criterions (Chen and Gupta, 1997). Going beyond the normal distributions, methods to detect parameter changes in poisson or exponential distributions were introduced (Truong et al., 2018; Chen and Gupta, 2000; Beaulieu et al., 2012). Hypothesis testing for parametric methods is challenging. Despite distributional

Figure 2.1: Examples of time series with change points of different nature. The red dashed lines show the timing of the change point.

assumptions, the distribution of the test statistic under the null hypothesis of no change is difficult to obtain. To approximate this distribution, approaches such as asymptotic theory, Monte Carlo methods or the Bonferroni inequality are used (Beaulieu et al., 2012; Niu et al., 2016). The parametric single change point detection methods can be extended to the multiple setting by an iterative application of the single method (Truong et al., 2018). For example, binary segmentation starts with the whole time series and tests for a single breakpoint. If significant, the time series is split up at the breakpoint and the test is applied to the two subsegments (Scott and Knott, 1974).

Non-Parametric Change Point Detection The drawback of parametric methods is that violations of the distributional assumptions may severely affect the results. In change point detection or - put the other way - test for homogeneity of data a vicious circle arises: for a parametric model a statistical homogeneity in form of the distribution is assumed, but the same model is used to evaluate the statistical homogeneity hypothesis (Brodsky and Darkhovsky, 1993). As in other statistical fields rank-based approaches are a popular non-parametric choice, for example modifications of the Mann-Whitney statistic (Pettitt, 1979; Lanzante, 1996). Another approach by Matteson and James (2014) uses a divergence measure based on Euclidean distance that also allows for multivariate data. Graph-based methods work with distances or generalized dissimilarity in the sample space that are reflected in a graph (Aminikhanghahi and Cook, 2016). Boracchi et al. (2018) use histograms to describe densities and thereby enable a monitoring of changes in distributions.

Regression-based Change Point Detection The regression-based approaches, if hypothesis testing is involved, adapt the testing scheme 2.1 by replacing changing distributions with linear regression coefficients (see also section 4.4). The alternative is a piecewise regression where the linear relationship changes abruptly at one or several unknown instants (Truong et al., 2018). The search for breakpoints is often performed within the residuals and can yield an estimate of the breakpoint location (Lyubchich et al., 2020) or tests for any unspecific change (Zeileis, 2005). Furthermore, F-Statistics can be used to compare the goodness of model fits with and without breakpoints via Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) (Chow, 1960; Banesh et al., 2019). RSS can further be used as a cost function in the optimization scheme in 2.2 to locate breakpoints. The optimal number of breakpoints is either retrieved in advance as by Bai and Perron (2003) or concurrently with their location estimates as by Tomé and Miranda (2004). The issue of an unknown test statistic distribution in hypothesis testing, as mentioned for parametric methods, also applies to some regression-based methods.

Method Selection The literature does not yield a single or a few dominant methods that are most commonly used throughout various disciplines. It rather seems like new breakpoint detection schemes are constantly evolving. Thus, the choice of the appropriate change point detection method depends on the particular dataset and the aim of the study. Militino et al. (2020); Sharma et al. (2016); Reeves et al. (2007); van den Burg and Williams (2020) have all assessed the performance of various methods using simulated or real-world data. None of the studies revealed striking differences in performance among the methods. For most methods performance was higher if the simulated magnitude of change was higher and the changes did not occur at the very beginning or end of the time series (Militino et al., 2020; Reeves et al., 2007).

As in many statistical fields there is no "one-size-fits-all" solution to the change point problem. The choice of a breakpoint detection method has to be based on criteria like the expected number of breakpoints, whether a location estimate is desired, the available computational resources or if distributional assumptions are realistic. In some cases the solution might not be a single method but rather an ensemble of several methods. For real-world data usually no ground truth data is available for evaluation. Comparing the results of different methods or different hyperparameter settings could be a useful approach. Searching for explanations, i.e. drivers of the change and thus checking the real-world probability of the breakpoints is essential in any case.

2.1.2 Applications in Environmental Analyses

Before moving on to the more specific vegetational applications, change point detection in environmental sciences will now be discussed more broadly. The available time series of environmental data - be it climatic, oceanographic, atmospheric or vegetational data - have constantly grown longer, enabling the detection of long term trends. At the same time, by reason of their length and effects of climate change, the time series might include breakpoints, subtrends or trend reversals. These changes might be omitted when solely looking at monotonic long term trends (Beaulieu and Killick, 2018; Sharma et al., 2016; De Jong et al., 2012; Forkel et al., 2013). Change point detection can be a useful tool to gain greater knowledge of various environmental changes, their duration, severity and spatial distribution as well as dependencies and feedback mechanisms on other processes. Breakpoints can be caused by abrupt disturbances like fire or floods, or by more gradual internal systematic changes, for example in climate variables such as yearly rainfall, atmospheric CO₂ concentrations or temperature (De Jong et al., 2013; Verbesselt et al., 2010).

Figure 2.2: Classification scheme for change point detection methods with examples for each branch in the bottom cell.

Climate tipping points are understood as critical thresholds or states at which small changes can have major impacts, causing an often irreversible long-term alteration of an ecological system. Prominent examples are the potential collapse of the Atlantic thermohaline circulation or the decay of the Greenland ice sheet (Lenton et al., 2008). So called regime shifts are based on a similar notion. Observations have shown that nature does not necessarily respond linearly or in a smooth way to gradual change. Gradual change can be interrupted by a rapid reorganization of a system from one relatively steady state to another. On a small scale this can be human-induced eutrophication of lakes, on a larger scale regime shifts in oceanic ecosystems have been observed for example in the 1970s and 1980s in the North Pacific (Scheffer et al., 2001; Hare and Mantua, 2000).

Examples Hence, the detection of change points can provide valuable insights in various disciplines within the environmental sciences. It has been applied to oxygen depletion in marine ecosystems and associated possible regime shifts (Lyubchich et al., 2020). In oceanography Banesh et al. (2019) have used change point detection to identify the emergence of ocean eddies, circular currents of water that affect the weather conditions in the ocean as well as its biological network. Thinking in time scales larger than a few decades, paleoclimatic records like Antarctic ice cores or benthic sediment cores have also been subjected to a change point analysis. It is often aimed at providing a more flexible framework for the detection of singular events or regime shifts than the common frequency-based approaches like Fourier or wavelet transformation (Ruggieri et al., 2009; Banesh et al., 2019). The analysis of climatic variables like land surface temperature and precipitation values are a common change point detection task, using both station data (Tomé and Miranda, 2004) and remote sensing products (Militino et al., 2020). Cermak et al. (2010) have studied breakpoints in satellite-derived aerosol and cloud datasets. Linking the idea of tipping points or regime shifts more closely to their drivers, change point detection methods can not only be applied to time series to identify the timing of a breakpoint. Instead a breakpoint can be the critical values of ecological parameters that may cause abrupt responses. D’Amario et al. (2019) have looked for breakpoints in nitrogen concentrations in aquatic systems that provoke structural and functional responses of bacterial and mussel communities as well as changes in water quality parameters. Aspin et al. (2019) studied macroinvertebrate communities’ responses to intensifying drought stress.

Applied Methods With respect to the methods chosen, the variety in environmental sciences is as large as in any other discipline. Many authors adapt and combine methods for their specific use cases. With reference to the previous section, studies in the field have applied parametric methods looking for changes in the mean (Beaulieu et al., 2012)

or variance (Killick et al., 2010), non-parametric rank-based methods (Lanzante, 1996; Militino et al., 2020) as well as adaptations of a piecewise linear regression approach (Banesh et al., 2019; Cermak et al., 2010; Tomé and Miranda, 2004) and structural change tests (Valt and Cianfarra, 2010; Lyubchich et al., 2020). Bayesian and online approaches, not covered in the previous section are also applied (Seidou et al., 2007; Rasmussen, 2001; Rodionov, 2004; Verbesselt et al., 2012). For selective overviews see Militino et al. (2020), who have compared different change point detection methods for remote sensing data and Reeves et al. (2007) for a review in climatology.

Seasonality and temporal autocorrelation An inherent feature of many environmental variables is seasonality. This cyclical behaviour of the data has to be taken into account, otherwise seasonal correlation structures might hinder the change analysis. One approach to tackle this issue is time series decomposition. The signal is decomposed into trend, seasonal and noise components before identifying breakpoints in one or more components. Several change point approaches using time series decomposition have been proposed, using an ensemble of different methods (Jamali et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2019; Forkel et al., 2013; Goela et al., 2016; Quan et al., 2016). One of the most commonly used is Breaks For Additive Seasonal and Trend (BFAST) by Verbesselt et al. (2010). Another approach to diminish seasonal effects is to aggregate all values of a year or a certain period of the year. However, after a decomposition or annual aggregation, values might still exhibit temporal autocorrelation (Watts and Laffan, 2014), which is known to worsen the performance of various change point detection methods (Robbins et al., 2011; Militino et al., 2020; Lund et al., 2007; Beaulieu et al., 2012). Autocorrelation can produce patterns in time series that are easily confounded with change points and regime shifts (Beaulieu et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2010). So, in the presence of temporal autocorrelation, a main challenge of change point detection is to distinguish signals of shifts and long term trends from internal variability and memory. Beaulieu and Killick (2018) present possible pitfalls in change point detection. As mentioned, serial autocorrelation can be misinterpreted as shifts in the mean (Figure 2.3 d), but also as a monotonic trend (Figure 2.3 c). In reverse, an autocorrelation-based model may be fitted erroneously, when a change in mean is actually present (Figure 2.3 e). In order to avoid confusing a mean shift with a monotonic trend (Figure 2.3 a), change point detection is often implemented in the first place.

To tackle the issue of temporal autocorrelation, different strategies have been developed. Data can be decorrelated beforehand, e.g. with a pre-whitening procedure. However, the original pre-whitening by von Storch (1999) is only useful "when we have physical reasons to assume that the considered time series is a sum of a trend and stochastic

Figure 2.3: Possible pitfalls when inferring changes from a time series that shows monotonic trend, shifts or serial autocorrelation as in Beaulieu and Killick (2018), p. 9521: a) a monotonic linear trend is fitted when a shift in mean or trend is present, b) a shift in mean is fitted when a monotonic trend is present, c) a linear trend is fitted assuming independent errors (white noise) when autocorrelation is present, d) shifts in mean are fitted assuming independent errors when autocorrelation is present and e) an AR(1) model is fitted when a shift in mean is present.

fluctuations generated by an AR(1) process” (von Storch, 1999, p. 17). It can be adapted for higher autoregressive orders, but in change point detection it still suffers from the possible confusion of a (mean) shift and an autocorrelation structure as in Figure 2.3 d) and e). A pre-whitening procedure would level out shifts in the signal, presuming they are part of an autocorrelation structure. Furthermore, in the analysis of thousands of time series, as in the case of gridded environmental data, it does not seem appropriate to assume the same autocorrelation structure for every grid cell. Several methods have been developed that consider temporal autocorrelation within the procedure instead of a preliminary decorrelation, like Lund et al. (2007); Robbins et al. (2011); Ma et al. (2020). Beaulieu and Killick (2018) have proposed a model selection approach where several model fits with combinations of different autocorrelation structures, shifts in mean or regression

parameters and monotonic trends are compared based on an information criterion. As they allow for multiple change points this can result in a high number of parameters and corresponding degrees of freedom which might result in reduced power. Lyubchich et al. (2020) also implement a model selection approach using BIC, however only in the choice of autoregressive order of the residuals of a linear regression model.

Artificial Shifts Finally it is important to mention that change point detection in environmental sciences is not only used to detect changes in environmental processes, but also to identify irregularities in the measurement process to ensure high quality and homogeneity of the data (Reeves et al., 2007). Depending on the technology involved, artificial shifts in environmental time series can stem from relocations of stations, changes in instrumentation or observation practice (Lanzante, 1996; DeGaetano, 2006). For remotely sensed data this could be a change of platform or sensor.

The methods and their rationale, applied in the two use cases - detection of artificial or ecological shifts - do not differ fundamentally. It is therefore crucial to check the data and its processing procedure carefully to avoid a misinterpretation of the source of breakpoints. In the detection of artificial shifts metadata of station history or reference series of spatial proximity might be consulted (Li and Lund, 2015; DeGaetano, 2006; Reeves et al., 2007).

2.1.3 Change Points in Global Greening and Browning Trends

Because of its various interactions within the earth system, vegetation cover structure and its changes are an important and widely studied ecological feature. As summarized in the IPCC special report *Climate Change and Land*, studies on long term monotonic vegetation trends have mostly agreed on an overall global greening trend over the last decades (IPCC, 2019, p. 143). Applying Mann-Kendall's Trend test to three different LAI datasets ranging from 1982 to 2009, Zhu et al. (2016) report greening over 25–50 % and browning over less than 4 % of the global vegetated area. Chen et al. (2019a) present similar estimations of greening and browning extents for a 2000-2017 record. Greening has been observed notably in southern Amazonia, India, eastern China, southeast Australia, the Sahel and many parts of Europe (IPCC, 2019; De Jong et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2019a; Fensholt et al., 2012; Pan et al., 2018). Browning has been detected in regions including northern Eurasia, southwestern USA, central South America and inner Asia (Pan et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2016; IPCC, 2019).

However, there are reasons for a more detailed and flexible investigation of vegetation dynamics than monotonic trend analysis. Future greening in response to rising temperature and extended growing season might saturate, as the correlation coefficient between temper-

ature and greenness has decreased over the last decades in northern latitudes (Piao et al., 2014; Vickers et al., 2016). In the tropics the temperature is already close to vegetation optimal temperature (Piao et al., 2019). Also land management strategies might change over time. Chen et al. (2019a) found land-management to be one of the major greening drivers in India and China in the last 20 years. Thus, change point detection and the analysis of resulting segments might exhibit changes in direction and magnitude of trends or reveal periods of no trends followed by trend onsets. This facilitates, with limitations, monitoring the effects of land management changes and the influence of climatic conditions on vegetation dynamics (De Jong et al., 2012). Change point detection studies dealing with greening and browning most commonly use offline approaches³. Regression-based methods are a popular choice since they easily allow the characterization of subtrends. Looking for changes in regression coefficients rather than in distributional parameters allows gradual trends in subsegments and avoids misinterpretation of a gradual trend as breakpoint/change in distributional parameters.

Regional Change Point Studies Wang et al. (2011) have detected trend reversals in spring and summer NDVI in North America throughout 1982 - 2006 with corresponding temperature dynamics, showing the strong temperature dependency of mid to high latitude vegetation growth in North America. Using a piecewise linear regression the differing trend segments could be detected, whereas a monotonic trend analysis showed only weak overall trends. The Breaks For Additive Season and Trend (BFAST) approach was applied in Sub-Saharan Africa by Higginbottom and Symeonakis (2020) using NDVI and rain use efficiency data. Although monotonic greening trends prevailed, in some regions reversals or amplification of trends were observed. For example in South Africa, they are possibly linked to shrub encroachment, or in Central Africa potentially associated with agricultural expansion. Cao et al. (2018) have studied the Chinese Loess Plateau with a piecewise linear regression, revealing even higher greening rates in the last 1-2 decades than before. Within the same time range a wetting trend was observed and major soil erosion control measures and afforestation programs were implemented. Chen et al. (2014) compared model fits of a simple linear regression and two piecewise approaches with one breakpoint for the Asia-Pacific region from 1982 to 2011. Greening prevailed in all regions and significant breakpoints mainly separated greening segments of different slope values. No major trend reversals occurred. Compared to other studies of shorter time spans the slope values for overall linear regression were smaller. Further regional change point detection studies on vegetation trends were conducted e.g. in Eastern China Grasslands (Liu et al., 2019), in

³Applications of online change point detection in remote sensing time series face several challenges, see Verbesselt et al. (2012).

Alaska (Forkel et al., 2013) or eastern Canada (Fang et al., 2018).

Global Change Point Studies On a global level De Jong et al. (2012, 2013) and Pan et al. (2018) have applied breakpoint detection to long term vegetation datasets, all three using the AVHRR based GIMMS3g NDVI time series. De Jong et al. (2012) performed a global change point detection with BFAST for a 1982 to 2008 time span. De Jong et al. (2013) used methods from BFAST but not within the iterative framework of the original algorithm to analyse NDVI data for 1981 till 2011. Pan et al. (2018) compared the outcomes of an ensemble empirical mode decomposition (EEMD) method with two piecewise linear regression models for 1982 to 2013. De Jong et al. (2012) allowed for up to 4 breakpoints, whereas De Jong et al. (2013) and Pan et al. (2018) limited the analyses to maximum one breakpoint, to identify only the major change within the study period. De Jong et al. (2013) and Pan et al. (2018) derived a classification scheme for different types of changes, which included monotonic greening/browning, an ongoing greening/browning trend that exhibits a setback/burst and trend reversals from greening to browning and vice versa (also see section 4.5). A classification of this type is clearer and more feasible in the case of one change point only.

All studies confirm the prevailing greening trends throughout the last decades with restrictions. De Jong et al. (2012) showed long periods of greening (> 20 years) in various regions of the northern hemisphere and greening prevailed in all land cover classes. Even though they found gradual greening to decrease globally and areas of browning to increase, there was still an overall increasing trend in global vegetation activity in recent years. Most of the breakpoints detected, which were up to 4 per pixel, separated segments with significant slopes from insignificant ones. 14.5% of the total land surface showed a swap in coefficient sign, exhibiting both greening and browning within the study period. A lot of those shifts were found in semi arid but also in temperate regions in Europe and North America.

In the study of De Jong et al. (2013) greening also prevailed, though it often included a setback which made the change type of interrupted greening the most common class. However, trend reversals also appeared, the majority being of type greening to browning. They mainly occurred in the late 1990s and early 2000s in Western Australia, the Sahel, Argentina, northern Kazakhstan and the Middle East. At the end of the study period the area of browning had increased by 40%. The number of breakpoints detected rose continuously with time, which the authors interpreted as higher turnover rates compared to rather stable vegetation regimes in the early years of the record.

Pan et al. (2018) also found that the extents of browning trends had increased throughout

their study period by more than twice. In line with De Jong et al. (2013) overall greening trends prevailed and among the reversals the greening to browning type was prevalent. After pixels with insignificant trend in both segments, greening to browning was the overall most common change type class. These reversals were characterized by widespread greening trends before the change points and expanding and strengthening browning trends afterwards.

All studies conclude that possible trend interruptions would have been overlooked and separate periods of significant change might have been averaged out when looking solely for monotonic trends.

Limitations and Challenges For any analysis of remotely sensed vegetational data, it has to be considered that a mere increase of NDVI or LAI does not necessarily correspond with a qualitative improvement in terms of biodiversity or ecosystem health (IPCC, 2019, p. 142). Results can stem from changes in the density of plants, average leaf size, number of leaves per plant, species composition or duration of green-leaf presence (Chen et al., 2019a). The indicators of vegetation productivity should be interpreted within the local ecological context (Higginbottom and Symeonakis, 2020).

For densely vegetated areas like the tropics, LAI and NDVI are known to likely saturate. Furthermore, this is an area with high cloud contamination, making the estimates less reliable, also reflected in large discrepancies among different products in this region (Piao et al., 2019; Xiao et al., 2017; Beck et al., 2011).

Furthermore, artificial sources of breakpoints have also to be kept in mind. For AVHRR based long term records, these are mainly changes of platforms and sensors, see section 4.1.

As in any other analysis of gridded environmental data that includes hypothesis testing, the multiple testing problem should be considered. Due to the possibly large number of single tests performed, the probability of false positive results is elevated. The statistical background of the multiple testing problem as well as common solutions are presented in the next section.

2.2 Multiple Testing Problem

In a setting where hypothesis tests of any kind are performed multiple times with different subsets of a data set, the multiple testing problem, also termed multiple comparison problem or multiplicity, arises.

2.2.1 Statistical Background

In a hypothesis test, a formulated null hypothesis H_0 will be rejected in favor of an alternative hypothesis H_1 , if the value of the test statistic is sufficiently extreme, i.e. above a defined threshold. An α -level is specified that represents the probability of falsely rejecting a true H_0 , thus the remaining margin of error allowed for in the test. H_0 is rejected at the α -level, if the probability of observing the current test statistic value, called the p-value, is no larger than α . If several hypotheses K are tested, as with environmental gridded data, different outcomes are possible Table 2.1. Out of R hypotheses, that were declared significant, S were correctly identified, whereas V represents erroneous rejections. For the remaining hypotheses $K - R$, that were declared non-significant, this was correct for U tests and false for T . Now if a family of K hypothesis tests with true null hypotheses are performed, we would expect αK of those tests to be false "discoveries" (V). For example for 100 tests performed ($K = 100$) at an α -level = 0.05, that would equal to $V = 5$ expected erroneous H_0 rejections.

Table 2.1: Variables representing the possible outcomes of testing K hypotheses.

	<i>Declared non-significant</i>	<i>Declared significant</i>	<i>Total</i>
True null hypotheses	U	V	K_0
False null hypotheses	T	S	$K - K_0$
	$K - \mathbf{R}$	R	K

For a particular set of tests, this portion might not be exactly αK , but can be rather seen as drawn from a probability distribution with mean αK . In Table 2.1 the erroneous rejections are represented by the unobservable random variable \mathbf{V} . If the test results are independent, the number of erroneous H_0 rejections can be modeled by a binomial distribution. For a single test, α can be seen as the *individual error rate*. In a setting of multiple tests, the mentioned probability of at least one erroneous rejection, $P(\mathbf{V} \geq 1)$, is called the *familywise error rate* FWER (also *global level* or *experimentwise error rate*). Following the binomial model, the FWER is already 0.994 for $K = 100$ and α -level = 0.05 (see Figure 2.4), further increasing with the number of tests. In the context of a remote

sensing analysis with hundreds or thousands of pixels, some true null hypotheses will most probably be rejected erroneously. Although the number of these false discoveries will be on average αK , the actual number might deviate considerably from αK . (Wilks, 2016; Katz and Brown, 1991; Heumann, 2015; Bender and Lange, 2001)

Figure 2.4: The probability of at least one false positive among a family of hypothesis tests (FWER) for an α -level = 0.05. FWER was modelled with a binomial distribution by number of tests performed, which is $P = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^K$.

Especially if the subsets of the data used in the tests are not independent, the binomial model is no longer valid, resulting in even higher probabilities for larger numbers of false rejections than αK . This is particularly relevant for environmental data which very often exhibit spatial autocorrelation. If no correction is applied, spatial autocorrelation can produce clusters of false positives and lead to spurious spatial patterns of significance (Wilks, 2006; Cortés et al., 2020). However, in the remote sensing community, the problem doesn't seem to be widely recognized (Heumann, 2015; Cortés et al., 2020). According to Wilks (2016), this also applies to the atmospheric sciences. In other disciplines like neuroimaging (Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003) or genetics (Balding, 2006), the issue is more commonly discussed.

Looking into existing methods to account for multiple testing, they can be divided into methods of strong and weak control of a chosen error rate (most commonly FWER or the False Discovery Rate (FDR), presented in the next section). For a family of tests, a global null hypothesis can be formulated, which states that all local/individual null hypotheses are true. Testing this global null hypothesis is also called testing for field significance (Wilks, 2016). A correction method with weak control only allows inference on this global null hypothesis. A method with strong control enables to reject or accept the local null

hypotheses as well as the global one (Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003; Bender and Lange, 2001). Thus a strong method offers control of the error rate no matter which or how many of the local null hypotheses are true. In environmental analysis, it is essential to make inferences on local tests and identify regional patterns of significance within the study area (Cortés et al., 2020). Hence, the approaches presented here all offer strong control.

A very common and simple solution to the multiple testing problem that controls FWER in a strong manner is the Bonferroni correction. A new threshold of significance is derived by dividing α by the number of simultaneous tests K . This correction has shown to be rather conservative, especially for a large number of performed tests, which is most often the case with remote sensing imagery. A search in the Web of Science, a big database for academic publications, only yielded 3 papers in the field of remote sensing that mentioned the keyword "bonferroni"⁴. The majority of remote sensing studies found, that applied any multiplicity correction, used the popular approach by Benjamini and Hochberg (1995). This approach offers strong control of the False Discovery Rate (FDR), weak control of the FWER, and is less conservative than the Bonferroni correction.

2.2.2 False Discovery Rate

The method by Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) to control the False Discovery Rate (FDR) (from here on referred to as BH) is related to the Bonferroni correction as both derive a new threshold of significance using the number of simultaneous tests performed. Additionally, the BH approach incorporates characteristics of the p-values-distribution resulting from the uncorrected tests. The FDR is the proportion of rejected null hypotheses that were rejected erroneously - \mathbf{S}/\mathbf{R} . As this cannot be observed, we deal with the expected proportion of errors among the rejected hypotheses, $E(\mathbf{S}/\mathbf{R})$. Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) argue for FDR instead of FWER as "*in many multiplicity problems the number of erroneous rejections should be taken into account and not only the question whether any error was made*". If all null hypotheses are true, the FDR is equal to the FWER anyhow and thus the BH method also provides weak control over FWER. In the case that one or more null hypotheses are false the FDR is smaller or equal to FWER. Any approach that controls the FWER also controls FDR, however, a method that controls FDR only is expected to have higher power (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). The BH approach is a step up procedure using the ordered p-values of k simultaneous tests. \mathcal{P}_i is the p-value at rank i with the corresponding null hypothesis H_i . Let m be the largest i for which holds

⁴The Web of Science was accessed via www.webofscience.com and the search was performed with the query "*TS=bonferroni AND WC=remote sensing*". The database does not allow scanning the whole content of a paper but only the abstract, title, and keywords.

$P_i \leq \frac{i}{K}\alpha$, then all $H_{ii} = 1, 2, \dots, m$ are rejected, with FDR controlled at α . For a detailed description of the procedure see Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) and Wilks (2006).

In their paper, Heumann (2015) aim to raise awareness for the multiple testing problem in the remote sensing community. In a search in the Web of Science catalog they found 7 remote sensing papers that cited Benjamini and Hochberg (1995). Redoing the request, the number has increased to 26 papers as of 24th June 2021. Watts et al. (2012) have used FDR control in change detection of surface water inundations in the Arctic–Boreal region using microwave satellite data. Xu et al. (2014) applied the BH procedure on classification techniques for marine oil spill identification in radar data and Mhawish et al. (2021) in the characterization of aerosols over South Asia. Most studies briefly mention to have applied the correction procedure, but only a few go into the theoretical background or details on the precise implementation or effects of the correction.

Although designed for independent data, the BH procedure and adjusted approaches showed to be rather robust in the presence of spatial autocorrelation (Wilks, 2006, 2016; Ventura et al., 2004). However, even if FDR control is less conservative than previous FWER controlling procedures, Cortés et al. (2020) have shown in a simulation study that a non-parametric permutation-based maximum statistic approach outperformed the BH method, proposing this new approach as a powerful alternative for multiple testing correction in remote sensing analysis.

2.2.3 Permutation-based Maximum Statistic Correction

The permutation-based method for multiplicity correction derives a new threshold from an empirical maximum statistic distribution and is able to control FWER in a strong manner. The non-parametric technique has been applied in disciplines like neuroimaging (Winkler et al., 2016; Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003) and genetics (Dudoit et al., 2003) and was introduced to the remote sensing community by Cortés et al. (2020).

Maximum Statistic The maximum statistic $\max T$ is crucial in FWER control, as one or more test statistics will exceed a threshold u if, and only if the maximum exceeds this threshold – recalling the FWER as the probability of at least one erroneous rejection. This connection can be used to establish an FWER-controlling threshold from the distribution of the maximum statistic under the global H_0 (Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003; Cortés et al., 2020). To control FWER at α_{global} , we choose u to be the $100 \cdot (1 - \alpha_{global})$ -th percentile of the maximum statistic distribution: $u_{\alpha_{global}} = F_{\max T | H_{global}=0}^{-1}(1 - \alpha_{global})$. The test

statistic of each hypothesis is denoted with T_i . Thus $u_{\alpha_{\text{global}}}$ controls FWER weakly:

$$\begin{aligned} P\left(\bigcup_i T_i \geq u \mid H_{\text{global}} = 0\right) &= P(\max T \geq u \mid H_{\text{global}} = 0) \\ &= 1 - F_{\max T \mid H_{\text{global}}=0}(u) \\ &= \alpha \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

This $u_{\alpha_{\text{global}}}$ also provides strong control of FWER if the assumption of subset pivotality is satisfied. A family of tests meets this assumption if there are no logical constraints among the results of individual tests (Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003). In the case of gridded environmental data, that means all combinations of significant and insignificant grid cells are possible. This is usually satisfied, as a test statistic coming from a test at one particular grid cell does not influence test statistic values at any other cell (Cortés et al., 2020). So any test statistic exceeding u is declared significant, whereas u can be derived from any valid test statistic. Equivalently a p-value-based threshold can be obtained using the minimum p-value distribution instead of the maximum statistic.

Permutation Procedure The non-parametric permutation procedure is performed to derive an *empirical* maximum statistic distribution, which determines threshold u . Hence, no assumptions on a theoretical distribution of the test statistic under the null hypothesis are needed. Permutation is based on resampling of the data itself. Unlike bootstrapping it is done *without* replacement, for example in a time series time points are rearranged randomly. In a satellite image or the image of a brain in neuroimaging, the images are resampled as a whole, instead of doing it pixel/voxel-wise to preserve spatial dependence. To perform a permutation test the data must meet the assumption of exchangeability. This is, that the distribution of the test statistic does not change under the null hypothesis if data is reordered/relabelled. For example, if we test for a change point in a time series, we state the null hypothesis that no change point exists, meaning that values are random and could have been observed at any time point and thus are interchangeable. Temporal autocorrelation violates the assumption of exchangeability and should be considered, e.g. by decorrelating the data series beforehand (Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003).

The permutation test is performed as follows. The data is rearranged in all possible ways, depending on the data size only a subsample of all combinations might be feasible. For each rearrangement/permutation the chosen test is performed at the individual level e.g. at every grid cell for remote sensing data and the maximum test statistic of the whole image is recorded. All sampled maximum statistics throughout the permutations form the empirical

distribution and the p-value of an original, unpermuted test is given by the fraction of test statistics in the empirical distribution greater than or equal to the observed test statistic (Cortés et al., 2020; Nichols and Hayasaka, 2003). For a number of n permutations, the lowest possible p-value thus is $\frac{1}{n}$. The p-values derived from the empirical distribution are also called *corrected* p-values, to differentiate them from the initial *uncorrected* p-values, that stem from the particular test applied and its corresponding theoretical test statistic distribution.

Suprathreshold Cluster Size As mentioned above, in environmental research a multiple testing correction with strong control of FWER is essential to identify particular regions of significant change. Furthermore, spatial autocorrelation might lead to spatial clusters of false positive results in a multiple testing setting. Using suprathreshold cluster size as a maximum statistic in the permutation-based correction is an attempt to distinguish false significant clusters arising from spatial autocorrelation from true significant ones.

In the permutation procedure, suprathreshold clusters are defined as adjacent significant grid cells. Significance is inferred using uncorrected p-values from the chosen test at a local significance level α_{local} . Suprathreshold cluster size (STCS) is thus the number of grid cells a particular suprathreshold cluster contains. So after performing tests at all grid cells of a permuted image, suprathreshold clusters are derived and the size, i.e. number of pixels, of the biggest cluster is recorded as the maximum statistic for each permutation. The local significance level α_{local} is only used for the definition of clusters (threshold for *uncorrected* p-values), whereas the global level of significance α_{global} defines the level at which FWER is controlled (threshold for *corrected* p-values) and is not influenced by α_{local} . Thus they can be set individually, setting them to an equal level might avoid confusion. Although regions of significance can be pinpointed using the STCS approach, the method formally does not allow inference on individual tests/grid cells. Significance is declared for the cluster as a whole.

To demonstrate the procedure we consider a time series of five yearly satellite images (see Table 2.2). For each permutation the years are shuffled and a hypothesis test is performed at every grid cell. Adjacent significant pixels are combined to form suprathreshold clusters. For each permutation, the size of the biggest cluster (STCS) is recorded as the maximum statistic. The rank shows the position of each maximum STCS in their empirical distribution in descending order. For five observations there are 120 possible ways to rearrange the time series ($5! = 120$). At an α -level of 0.05, a cluster is declared significant, if its size is equal to or larger than the sixth-largest STCS value in the empirical distribution

Table 2.2: Example of permutation procedure with a short time series and suprathreshold cluster size (STCS) as maximum statistic.

Data	Maximum STCS	Rank
<i>Original Data:</i> 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004	12000	3
<i>Permutation 1:</i> 2001, 2003, 2000, 2004, 2002	16000	1
<i>Permutation 2:</i> 2003, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2004	7000	9
...
...
<i>Permutation 120:</i> 2004, 2002, 2000, 2003, 2001	9000	6

in the current demonstration, as $120 \cdot 0.05 = 6$. Here this would apply to all clusters within the original data that are composed of at least 9000 pixels. To derive corrected p-values, we divide the rank of the cluster within the empirical distribution by the number of rearrangements. For a cluster of size 12000, $p_{corr} = 3/120 = 0.025$.

Cortés et al. (2020) have analyzed the STCS permutation procedure in a simulation study, introducing different levels of spatial autocorrelation as well as different intensities and spatial extents of trends to random data. They have compared the STCS and $\max T$ permutation-based approach to BH and modifications thereof as well as Bonferroni-related FWER controlling procedures. For global test power (the proportion of images with correctly identified field significance), as for within image test power (the proportion of correctly identified grid cells) STCS shows good results and higher power than the other correction methods. This proposes the permutation-based STCS approach as a powerful method for multiple testing correction in remote sensing applications that accounts for spatial autocorrelation. However, Cortés et al. (2020) have identified that STCS performance is worse in the case of small trend-induced regions and strong spatial autocorrelation. This is explicable as only cluster size but no individual, i.e. grid cell test statistic/p-values are considered. With stronger spatial autocorrelation randomly appearing clusters become bigger than trend regions, concealing them from the STCS method. Combining both cluster size and test statistic/p-values in the Tippett combining function as proposed by Poline et al. (1997) and Hayasaka and Nichols (2004) might enable detecting smaller clusters.

Chapter 3

Research Design

In the analysis of gridded environmental data using hypothesis tests the multiple testing problem should be considered to ensure reliable and robust results. Cortés et al. (2020, 2021) and Heumann (2015) have tried to raise awareness for the issue, which has not been recognized widely in the field of remote sensing so far. Many methods in change point detection rely on hypothesis testing, though to the author's knowledge there is no study on vegetation breakpoints so far, that has corrected for multiple testing on the image level. The main goal of this study was to introduce multiple testing correction into a change point detection procedure. The following research questions were posed:

1. Does a multiple testing correction combining STCS and maximum cluster statistic offer a more sensitive approach for detecting smaller significant clusters than STCS alone?
2. How do results of change point detection on global LAI time series differ when correcting for multiple testing?
3. Overlaying the results of change point detection and monotonic long term trend tests - does the latter omit possible breakpoints and subtrends?
4. Which global image regarding occurrence and types of breakpoints is presented by the corrected results compared to previous studies?
5. Is the permutation-based procedure for multiple testing correction by Cortés et al. (2020) easily transferable to another environmental use case?

Figure 3.1: Flowchart of steps in the research process.

To answer these questions the Tippet Combining Function (TCF) was implemented, an adjusted version of the STCS procedure that includes test statistic intensities. To check its sensitivity to smaller clusters, it was applied to the results of a Mann Kendall Trend Test of the LAI data record. In the main part, a change point detection was performed using our adjusted version of MCUSUM by Lyubchich et al. (2020). We corrected for multiple testing with the manual combination procedure, a further modification of TCF, which was necessary due to computational constraints (section 4.4). Change point detection results were overlaid with the monotonic trend results of Mann Kendall Test of the first part and different types of change were derived for the breakpoints. Figure 3.1 illustrates the steps of the research process. The following chapter gives a detailed outline of the data and methods used.

Chapter 4

Methods and Data

All statistical analyses were performed using the open source data analysis programming language R version 4.1.0 (R Core Team, 2020). The R-code developed for permutation-based STCS multiple testing correction was liberally provided by José Cortés (as used in Cortés et al. (2020, 2021)) and adjusted for the needs of this study. Maps were generated using the *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016), *stars* (Pebesma, 2021), and *sf* (Pebesma, 2018) packages. Computationally intensive permutation procedures were performed using the High Performance Server of the GIScience group, Institute of Geography, Friedrich-Schiller University Jena. The Code is available in a GitHub Repository (https://github.com/vroni-g/change_point_detection) and archived on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5211689>). The GitHub Repository includes detailed documentation in the ReadMe section, that explains the structure of the repository and the functionality of the scripts. The code is not fully reproducible as some of the input data is only stored on the HPC facilities, due to its large size. For more details see the code documentation on GitHub.

4.1 AVHRR based LAI Time Series

In change point analysis of vegetation time series NDVI is a common choice to represent estimates of photosynthetic activity (see section 2.1.3). Another eligible satellite product for vegetation monitoring used in the present analysis is LAI. LAI is recognized as an Essential Climate Variable by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) (GCOS, 2017) and yields a quantifiable value of the amount of vegetation on the ground. The Global Terrestrial Observing System (GTOS) specifies the LAI as follows: ” *The LAI [m_2/m_2] is geometrically defined as the total one-sided area of photosynthetic tissue per*

unit ground surface area” (Gobron and Verstraete, 2009). It can be measured *in situ* or derived from satellite imagery.

The AVHRR has sensed the earth throughout the last 40 years onboard the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration of the United States of America (NOAA) satellites, yielding the longest available time series of remote sensing data for global vegetation analysis (Table 4.2 shows the different platforms and sensors used for GIMMS3g NDVI values). The time span covered and the high temporal resolution make it a valuable data source, which however suffers from several well-known problems. This includes orbital drift of satellites, changes in platforms and sensors, sensor degradation, and inconsistent band calibration (Tian et al., 2015; Giglio and Roy, 2020; John et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2017; Beck et al., 2011). Various global NDVI and LAI products have been derived from AVHRR data using different methods for correction and calibration. In terms of absolute values but also regarding the trends obtained, inconsistencies among the datasets have been observed, leading to dissent on the magnitude and spatial extent of global greening and browning trends (Tian et al., 2015; Xiao et al., 2017; Jiang et al., 2017). Several studies thus investigate coinciding trends of different datasets (Cortés et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2019a; Zhu et al., 2016) or use averaged values of several datasets (Piao et al., 2019). The most widely used long term AVHRR based LAI products starting in 1981/1982 are Boston University GIMMS3g LAI (BU GIMMS3g), Global LAnd Surface Satellite (GLASS), Land Long Term Data Record (LTDR), and NOAA Climate Data Record (CDR) with varying data sources, temporal and spatial resolution and generation techniques (see Table 4.1).

Accuracy of both NDVI and LAI datasets has been assessed using field data (Xiao et al., 2017), or other reference remote sensing products like Landsat (Beck et al., 2011) or Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) (Tian et al., 2015; Jiang et al., 2017; Fensholt et al., 2012). However, for years before 2000, field data is scarcely available (Jiang et al., 2017; Fang et al., 2019), and MODIS only operates since 2000. Furthermore, MODIS data was used in the generation of some datasets and might also suffer from sensor degradation and resulting inconsistencies (Tian et al., 2015; Jiang et al., 2017) making accuracy assessment challenging. Thus an unequivocally best suited dataset can hardly be defined. In a comparison of NDVI datasets, both Beck et al. (2011); Tian et al. (2015) concluded that GIMMS3g NDVI - the basis of the corresponding LAI product by Boston University - showed the highest temporal consistency. Xiao et al. (2017) found that compared with field data GLASS performed better than NOAA CDR and GIMMS3g, though only with a difference of 0.2 in RMSE with LAI values spanning from 0 to 7. The use of any of the datasets requires careful interpretation as the products might not be equally af-

Table 4.1: Overview of widely used long term LAI products starting in 1981. For details on data generation see listed references and Xiao et al. (2017); Jiang et al. (2017) for short summaries. Bold dataset **BU GIMMS3g** is used in the present study.

Dataset	Input Data	Resolution	Quality flags	Reference
BU GIMMS3g	GIMMS3g NDVI, MODIS LAI	15-day, 1/12°	Yes	(Zhu et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2019a)
GLASS	LTDR AVHRR reflectance, CY-CLOPES and MODIS LAI	8-day, 0.05°	No	(Liang et al., 2013)
LTDR	LTDR AVHRR reflectance, MODIS LAI	daily, 0.05°	Yes	(Pedelty et al., 2007)
NOAA CDR	LTDR AVHRR reflectance, MODIS LAI	daily, 0.05°	Yes	(Claverie et al., 2016)

ected by inconsistencies throughout different biomes or humidity zones. Especially humid regions like tropical forests show high uncertainties and differences among datasets related to saturation effects of LAI and increased cloud cover (Tian et al., 2015; Xiao et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2019a; Jiang et al., 2017; De Jong et al., 2012). In the context of change point detection, major attention should be paid to the timing of platform changes to avoid a misinterpretation of breakpoints (De Jong et al., 2011; Tian et al., 2015).

A comparison of the results of several different datasets is beyond the scope of the study, which is directed towards methodical advances in the correction of the multiple testing problem. The analysis was performed using the BU GIMMS3g LAI dataset, since it performed well in the mentioned comparison studies and delivers quality flags, enabling a quality-based assessment of the results. Although we lose some precision due to the lower spatial resolution compared to the other datasets, this yields the advantage of reduced computational effort. The GIMMS3g NDVI dataset - the basis of the BU GIMMS3g LAI values - has been used in other global change point vegetation studies De Jong et al. (2012, 2013); Pan et al. (2018), making the current results somewhat comparable. The LAI values were derived using an artificial neural network algorithm, for details the reader is referred to Zhu et al. (2013); Chen et al. (2019a).

Table 4.2: The platform and sensor lineage used for GIMMS3g NDVI data, which is the database of BU LAI data. Derived from Pinzon and Tucker (2014); Tian et al. (2015).

AVHRR-2:
01/1982–02/1985 NOAA-7
03/1985–10/1988 NOAA-9
11/1988–08/1994 NOAA-11
09/1994–12/1994 NOAA-9
01/1995–10/2000 NOAA-14
AVHRR-3:
11/2000–12/2003 NOAA-16
01/2004–12/2008 NOAA-17
01/2009–12/2011 NOAA-18
since 01/2012 NOAA-19

4.2 Data Pre-processing

The BU GIMMS3g LAI dataset for 1981–2018 had been liberally provided to José Cortés by Ranga B. Myneni and Chi Chen from Boston University (used in Cortés et al. (2021)) and made available to me for use in the present study. To save computational effort barren land and ice were excluded from the analysis and masked beforehand using the MODIS Land Cover Climate Modeling Grid (Friedl and Sulla-Menashe, 2015). Only pixels with complete time series were included in the analysis. The year 1981 was excluded as the record started in the mid of the year and thus the mean of this year is biased.

Annual aggregation of time series Before starting the analysis the LAI values were aggregated annually. Annual aggregation of values reduces the temporal resolution and time series length, however, seasonal correlation structures hinder the trend and change analysis and have to be accounted for, e.g. in a time series decomposition (see section 2.1.2). Forkel et al. (2013) showed that annually aggregated data performed equally well in a simulation study of change point detection compared to different seasonal modeling approaches. Furthermore with regard to the permutation-based correction procedure, using aggregated values is more straightforward since seasonal correlation structures impair the data’s exchangeability (see section 2.2.3). Values can be summarized as mean, median, or different quantiles of the yearly range (Cortés et al., 2021; Forkel et al., 2013), as well as seasonal or growing season aggregates (Wang et al., 2011). For the sake of clarity and fewer levels of comparison only mean aggregates were used in the present study. The aggregation was performed using the *raster* (Hijmans, 2020) and *stars* (Pebesma, 2021) package.

Figure 4.1: The Percentage of Time Points at every Pixel labeled as either retrieved from spline interpolation (flag 1) or from seasonal profile because of snow/clouds (flag 2). Grey areas have no data or no quality issues at all.

The quality flags were delivered for every image of the dataset and thus needed to be aggregated as well. The existing flags were flag 0 for no apparent issues, flag 1 for values derived from spline interpolation, and flag 2 for values derived from the seasonal profile because of possible snow or cloud cover. For every pixel, a quality measure was obtained, namely the percentage of time points of the whole time series that exhibited either flag 1 or flag 2 (see Figure 4.1).

4.3 Tippet Combining Function

As shown in section 2.2, applying hypothesis tests multiple times, as in the analysis of satellite image time series can result in uncontrolled false positive rates and in conjunction with spatial autocorrelation in potentially misleading spatial patterns of erroneous "discoveries". To account for multiple testing, an adjusted version of the permutation-based Suprathreshold Cluster Size (STCS) approach by Cortés et al. (2020, 2021) was implemented.

Cortés et al. (2020) have shown in a simulation study that using STCS as maximum statistic offers a powerful correction method for the multiple testing problem. However, they have identified that STCS performance was worse in the case of small trend-induced regions and strong spatial autocorrelation. To enable the detection of smaller clusters a combination of both cluster size and test statistic value was implemented - the Tippet Combining

Function (TCF) W_i^T as proposed by Hayasaka and Nichols (2004). This combined test statistic is analogous to Poline et al. (1997)'s minimum p-value approach, rejecting H_0 if the smaller p-value of two partial tests is below the significance threshold. W_i^T includes the suprathreshold cluster size as well as the maximum test statistic value within a cluster, also called peak intensity (Hayasaka and Nichols, 2004)¹. Let \mathcal{P}_i^m be the corrected p-value for peak intensity of cluster i , and \mathcal{P}_i^s be the corrected p-value for the size of the same cluster, both derived from their respective empirical maximum statistic distribution (see section 2.2.3 for an in-depth explanation of how corrected p-values are obtained). The Tippett Combining Function W_i^T is then defined as

$$W_i^T = 1 - \min(\log \mathcal{P}_i^m, \log \mathcal{P}_i^s) \quad (4.1)$$

The corrected p-values and the W_i^T test statistics are derived using the same set of permutations to save computational effort. For each permutation, the position, size, and peak intensity of every cluster, as well as the maximum STCS value and the maximum peak intensity are recorded. Subsequently, for each cluster in each permutation using their respective size and peak intensity, corrected p-values are computed based on the empirical maximum distributions² and combined in W_i^T . For each permutation in turn the maximum W_i^T is recorded and the distribution formed thereby is used to test for significance of the suprathreshold clusters of the original non-permuted data set.

The TCF was implemented in R as an extension to Cortés et al. (2020)'s code. For cluster derivation, the *osc* package was used (Kriewald et al., 2019) and neighboring pixels were defined as contiguous first-order queen neighbors. Minimum cluster size was one.

It was applied to the BU GIMMS3g LAI time series using the Mann–Kendall's Trend test to compare the results to regular STCS and check its performance in the detection of smaller clusters.

¹Please note that the term peak intensity in neuroimaging applications might not only correspond to the mere maximum test statistic value within one suprathreshold cluster but to another maximum intensity measure that is derived based on assumptions of a gaussian random field and previous smoothing of the data. To avoid confusion with different usages of the term maximum statistic value, peak intensity is adopted nevertheless and only to be understood as explained here.

²The empirical maximum statistic distribution only contains the maximum statistic values but corrected p-value have to be obtained for every cluster in every permutation, not only the ones with maximum size or peak intensity. For the non-maximum values there was no value matching exactly in the empirical distribution and the next smaller existing value was used to derive the corrected p-value.

4.4 Change Point Detection with MCUSUM

For change point detection the modified CUSUM (MCUSUM) procedure by Lyubchich et al. (2020) was applied. It is an adaption of the at-most- m changes approach by Horváth et al. (2017) and aims to detect changes in coefficients of a linear regression model with potentially autocorrelated errors. Referring to Figure 2.2 it is an offline frequentist regression based methods, that - with our modifications - looks for a single breakpoint. Even though it performed rather conservatively compared to other change point detection methods in a simulation with random data (see appendix Table 7.1), its theoretical characteristics yield several advantages. For MCUSUM no particular dependence structure or distribution of the regression residuals is assumed. The method avoids asymptotic theory assumptions and estimation of the long-run variance function to derive significance thresholds as necessary in Horváth et al. (2017), by implementing a nonparametric sieve bootstrap procedure. This is also expected to enhance the performance of the test for small sample sizes (Lyubchich et al., 2020). At last, it allows for autocorrelation in the residuals within a flexible Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)-based model selection approach for the autoregressive order. This way no fixed autocorrelation structure for all grid cells, i.e. individual tests, has to be chosen, nor do we have to perform possibly problematic pre-whitening/decorrelation procedures beforehand (see section 2.1.2). Although the test does not assume independent errors, it does assume stationarity of the time series values and regression residuals and that the time series is a Bernoulli shift. This can be approximated with a finitely dependent time series (Lyubchich et al., 2020). For a thorough discussion see Horváth et al. (2017).

Procedure The modified CUSUM procedure tests for changes in the coefficients of a linear regression model

$$Y_t = X_t\beta_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4.2)$$

of a time series of length T ($t = 1, \dots, T$). Y_t is the response variable, X_t the regressor matrix, β_t is a vector of regression coefficients and ε_t the regression residuals. The model includes an intercept term. Adapting the testing scheme of Equation 2.1 - though for possibly more than one change point - we state the null hypothesis of constant regression coefficients :

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots = \beta_T \\ H_1 : \beta^{(j)} \neq \beta^{(l)} \quad \text{for some } 1 \leq j, l \leq m + 1, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where $\beta^{(i)}(i = 1, \dots, m + 1)$ are regression coefficients in the i th segment and τ_1, \dots, τ_m are the locations of m change points ($1 \leq \tau_1 \leq \tau_2 \leq \dots \tau_m < T$). The null hypothesis of no change will be rejected in all cases from minimum one change point to at most m change points, where the locations of the possible m change points have to be specified before applying the test.

To detect changes in the coefficients the regression residuals are used:

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_t = Y_t - X_t \hat{\beta}_t \tag{4.4}$$

with $\hat{\beta}_t$ estimated using Ordinary least squares (OLS). Assuming possible autoregressive dependence among the error terms, the OLS estimates are still unbiased. Fitting an autoregressive model of order p , with the corresponding autoregressive coefficients we can derive the residuals v_t of the autoregressive model. To get the modified CUSUM test statistic M_T , a test statistic is computed for every possible combination of one to m change points of the locations prespecified and then their maximum value is used. The test statistic is based on the residuals $\hat{\varepsilon}_t$, the involved change point locations τ_i and the length of the time series T . The detailed formula of the test statistic is accessible in Lyubchich et al. (2020). For example for three change points specified, $m = 3$, and their locations $\{1 \leq \tau_1 \leq \tau_2 \leq \tau_3 < T\}$, there are seven possible combinations that are used to derive the maximum: $\{(\tau_1), (\tau_2), (\tau_3), (\tau_1, \tau_2), (\tau_1, \tau_3), (\tau_2, \tau_3), (\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3)\}$. The combination that yields the largest test statistic value is also defined as the final change point locations.

Now in the complete procedure by Lyubchich et al. (2020) the following steps are executed:

1. The observed test statistic, $M_t^{(obs)}$, is computed based on $\hat{\varepsilon}_t$.
2. The autoregressive order p is chosen based on a model selection using BIC, autoregressive coefficients are estimated with the robust difference-based estimator of autocorrelation functions by Hall and Keilegom (2003).
3. The residuals of the autoregressive model \hat{v}_t are calculated. If the selected order p in step 2. is zero, then $\hat{v}_t = \hat{\varepsilon}_t$.
4. A bootstrap sample (i.e. with replacement) \hat{v}_t^* is taken from \hat{v}_t .
5. A new autoregressive series $\hat{\varepsilon}_t^*$ is created, using the autoregressive coefficients of step 2. and \hat{v}_t^* .
6. The bootstrapped test statistic, $M_t^{(*1)}$, is computed based on $\hat{\varepsilon}_t^*$.
7. Steps 4.-6. are repeated a large number of times and form the distribution of bootstrapped statistics $\{M_t^{(*b)}\}_{b=1}^B$, with B being the total number of bootstrap repetitions.

8. To test Equation 4.3, the bootstrap p-value is defined as the proportion of $\{M_t^{(*b)}\}_{b=1}^B$ that exceeds $M_t^{(obs)}$.

The procedure is available in the R-package *funtimes* using the function `mcusum_test` (Lyubchich and Gel, 2020).

Adjustments Mainly to reduce computing time, several adjustments have been made to the code of Lyubchich and Gel (2020) in collaboration with Prof. Alexander Brenning.³ As the test has to be performed for nearly 2 million grid cells per image and each permutation in the multiple testing correction gives a new image, even with High Performance Computing facilities and parallelization, it was necessary to shorten the per-test computing time to make calculations feasible.

The parts of the testing procedure with the highest computational cost were the bootstrapping and the iteration over all possible combinations, the number of which drastically rises with each additional change point. Thus, we implemented an adaptive bootstrapping, that includes a preliminary check after a quarter of the specified bootstrap iterations. After those first repetitions, we assess whether the observed test statistic is still able to reach a p-value of equal or below 0.1. Only for the test statistics who pass the test, the rest of the bootstraps are performed and an exact p-value is derived. For example, if the number of bootstrap repetitions is set to 1000, at most 100 of the bootstrap test statistics can be larger than the observed test statistic, to reach a p-value of 0.1. So if after 250 repetitions already 100 or more have a test statistic value above the observed one, the adaptive procedure will stop. Otherwise, the remaining 750 repetitions will be performed. Additionally, the bootstrap p-value was re-defined as the proportion of bootstrap statistics *equal to* or larger than the observed test statistic to avoid p-values of zero (see step 8. of the procedure outline above).

Furthermore, to reduce the number of combinations that have to be iterated, we limited the possible number of change points to one, an at-most-*one* change point test, so to say. We thereby aim to identify the most important shift throughout the time series (Forkel et al., 2013; De Jong et al., 2013). A single breakpoint also enables a clear classification into breakpoint types (section 4.5). In order to be able to test several different locations for that singular change point, multiple locations can be specified but the combinations tested are trimmed to only the ones with single change points. So in the example of the previous section with $m = 3$, the combinations would only be $\{(\tau_1), (\tau_2), (\tau_3)\}$. For the 37-year time series, 31 possible change point locations every year from 1985-2015 were

³Since August 14, 2021 our adjustments are also available in the *funtimes* R-package by Vyacheslav Lyubchich. The new parameter m is the maximum number of change points allowed, the parameter *shortboot* defines whether the adapted bootstrapping should be performed.

compared. The number of bootstrap repetitions was set to 500. The resulting p-values were used in the multiple testing correction in a minimum p-value approach instead of the maximum statistic.

Customized Combining Function Even with the adjustments and a second level of parallelization, the computing time for each test was still high compared to other methods. Furthermore, at the time of computation, the High Performance Server was heavily used, thus only a limited number of permutations in the multiple testing correction was possible. This combined with the quasi discrete p-values resulting from the bootstrap approach⁴ strongly diminished the power of the Tippet Combining Function as a multiple testing correction approach. The empirical distributions formed by the permutation and the bootstrapping were too discrete and too little variable to derive reasonable corrected p-values. Thus a manual combination of STCS and a cluster size dependent p-value threshold was applied.

In a first step, the empirical distribution of STCS from the permutations was used to define the STCS threshold at a given alpha level and all clusters above that threshold were declared significant. In a second step all clusters and their respective minimum p-value ($\hat{=}$ peak intensity) of all permutations but the original one, were analyzed jointly. Classes of cluster size were defined and for each size class, the 10th quantile (for $\alpha = 0.1$) of the minimum p-values was derived and set as the significance threshold for clusters of this size. This approach was chosen because of the high number of clusters in the very small size range. Back to the original image, after large clusters were declared significant by STCS alone, for the remaining clusters the minimum p-values were compared to the respective size-dependent threshold and significance was determined. The procedure is termed *manual combination* in the following sections.

4.5 Subtrends and Change Point Types

For all pixels declared significant with the manual combination approach, the time series was divided based on the change point timing estimate. For both segments, a Mann Kendall Trend Test was performed, and for segments significant at an α -level of 0.1, slope coefficients were derived with a simple linear regression. Although this actually represents a further multiple testing setting, no correction was applied as tests were only performed to get a rough overview of the type of changes detected and no robust inference was

⁴In the bootstrapping the p-values are derived the same way as corrected p-values in the permutation procedure (section 2.2.3). Thus the minimum p-value achieved by MCUSUM was $1/500 = 0.002$ and all p-values were multiplies of 0.002 between $1 - 0.002$.

desired. Depending on the significance of Mann Kendall Tests and the sign of the slope coefficients the pixels were classified into different change point types as annotated in Table 4.3. Segments of significant tests and positive or negative slope signs were labeled as greening and browning periods respectively. Pixels with non-significant Mann Kendall Tests in both segments were called *both non-significant* but are not listed in the change point type scheme of Table 4.3. Figure 4.2 shows artificial example time series to illustrate the change point types.

Table 4.3: Change Point Types based on Mann Kendall (MK) Trend Test and linear regression slope.

Change Point Type	First Segment	Second Segment
<i>Greening to Browning</i>	Significant MK, positive slope	Significant MK, negative slope
<i>Browning to Greening</i>	Significant MK, negative slope	Significant MK, positive slope
<i>Continued Greening</i>	Significant MK, positive slope	Significant MK, positive slope
<i>Continued Browning</i>	Significant MK, negative slope	Significant MK, negative slope
<i>Greening Onset</i>	Non-significant MK	Significant MK, positive slope
<i>Browning Onset</i>	Non-significant MK	Significant MK, negative slope
<i>Stalled Greening</i>	Significant MK, positive slope	Non-significant MK
<i>Stalled Browning</i>	Significant MK, negative slope	Non-significant MK

Figure 4.2: Artificial time series graphs showing the different possible types of change points. The red dashed line shows the timing of the change point. Colors in the upper right corner are used in maps in section 5.2 to differentiate change point types.

Chapter 5

Results

Following the research questions, firstly the results of the testing of TCF on the monotonic trend test will be presented. Secondly the estimated change points of MCUSUM with multiple testing correction as well as the overlay of change points and monotonic trends will be shown.

5.1 Sensitivity of Tippet Combining Function

A Mann Kendall Trend test was applied to the 1982-2018 BU GIMMS3g LAI annual mean time series without multiple testing correction, with STCS correction, and with TCF correction. The TCF detected 7 to 8 times more significant clusters than the STCS correction (see Table 5.1), whereas the increase in terms of the number of pixels and the corresponding earth surface area was not as large (16% increase in pixel, 14% increase in area). All clusters declared significant by STCS were also included by TCF, so the differing clusters were all below the cluster size threshold derived from STCS (see Figure 5.1). 51% of the TCF significant clusters had a size of even less than 50 pixels (for global

Table 5.1: Comparison of clusters declared significant in Mann Kendall Trend Test uncorrected for multiple testing, with STCS as well as TCF correction by number of clusters, number of pixels and total area of significant clusters for an alpha local and global of 0.1.

	Clusters	Pixels	Area (km^2)
Uncorrected	76,632	809,043	49,384,444
STCS	10	317,796	19,302,531
TCF	84	368,436	22,012,697

Figure 5.1: Size and TCF value of suprathreshold clusters of a Mann Kendall Trend test on the BU dataset. 1000 permutations were performed to derive empirical maximum statistic distributions for STCS and TCF. The corrected thresholds at a 0.1 and 0.05 α -level of both distributions are marked with a solid and dotted red line respectively.

and local alpha¹ = 0.1).

The STCS based significant clusters were only greening clusters (see Figure 5.2), whereas the TCF corrected results also included 16 browning clusters (8772 pixels, 716,489 km²), which equaled roughly 3% of the area of TCF significant clusters. Greening regions detected by TCF showed major clustering in west and central Africa, throughout Europe and western, central and eastern Russia, as well as India, eastern China, mid-east and northern North-America, and southern Brazil. Browning clusters that appeared with TCF correction were located in Madagascar, Mozambique, and Tanzania (Figure 5.2).

¹If not otherwise specified, a given alpha level refers to both global and local level.

Mann Kendall Trend Test Suprathreshold Cluster Size (STCS)

Tippet Combining Function (TCF)

Uncorrected Results

Alpha local = 0.1, Alpha global = 0.1

Figure 5.2: Global distribution of significant ($\alpha = 0.1$) greening and browning clusters for STCS, TCF and uncorrected results from Mann Kendall Trend Test on 1982-2018 BU LAI data. Barren land and ice covered areas were excluded from the analysis and are marked in white, water is blue.

Data quality 27% of the clusters declared significant by TCF exhibited severe quality issues with a median above 40% of per pixel time points with quality flags for spline interpolation or cloud/snow cover (see Figure 5.3). Mainly clusters with a size smaller than 50,000 pixels were affected, however not all clusters of this size range showed quality issues.

Figure 5.3: Size of TCF significant clusters and their median value of percentage of time points with quality issues. The size of the points corresponds to the interquartile range (IQR) within the cluster. Local and global alpha $\alpha = 0.1$.

5.2 Modified CUSUM

In the change point detection with modified CUSUM the Tippet Combining Function was not particularly useful because of the bootstrap procedure involved and the smaller amount of permutations performed due to computational limitations. Instead, a manual combination of STCS and a quantile-based minimum p-value thresholding was applied as explained in section 4.4. The results are based on 30 permutations. The size-dependent thresholds are denoted in Table 7.2 in the appendix. Including test statistics/p-values also yielded a higher number of significant pixels than STCS in change point detection as did the Tippet Combining Function on Mann Kendall Trend Test. Clusters declared significant merely because of size, which are those detected by STCS, made up 62% of the significant area in km^2 of manual combination correction (Table 5.2). Within the smaller clusters declared significant because of their minimum p-value, 61% had a size of fewer than 10 pixels (for a histogram of significant clusters grouped by size see Appendix Figure 7.1). The total number of uncorrected clusters, pixels, and area was much lower than with Mann Kendall Trend Test, however, the proportion of uncorrected clusters, pixels, and area declared significant after manual combination correction was much higher than with Tippet Combining Function and Mann Kendall Trend Test. Looking at the significant change point pixels with manual combination correction, they are scattered around the globe with bigger clusterings in west and central Africa, eastern China, as well as eastern Brazil, eastern Canada, and eastern Ukraine (Figure 5.4). Apart from the large clusters, the size distribution among the significant clusters after correction and the uncorrected cluster was rather similar (see Appendix Figure 7.2). Looking at the Bonferroni-related correction methods used in Cortés et al. (2020), none of these methods yielded any significant pixel after correction.

Table 5.2: Comparison of clusters declared significant in modified CUSUM uncorrected for multiple testing, with STCS as well as manual approach by number of clusters, number of pixels and total area of significant clusters in km^2 for an alpha local and global of 0.1.

	Clusters	Pixels	Area (km^2)
Uncorrected	844	46,467	2,907,926
STCS	12	21,505	1,482,777
Manual Combination	352	37,507	2,375,029

Figure 5.4: Global image of pixels with significant change points derived from modified CUSUM with 1982-2018 BU LAI data. Uncorrected results are in blue, STCS and manual combination correction are overlaid in yellow respectively. Barren land and ice covered areas were excluded from the analysis and are marked in white, water is blue.

Data quality Around 35 % of the significant clusters by manual combination had a median of more than 40 % of per-pixel quality issues within the 37 yearly values. There was no clear connection between cluster size and quality issues, quality issues seemed to be less severe for bigger clusters, but overall there were way fewer big clusters than small ones (see Appendix Figure 7.5).

Autoregressive Modelling The results of the modified CUSUM also delivered the autoregressive order that was chosen in the BIC-based model selection. Out of the 35,507 significant pixels, in 25,136 cases an AR(0) model was selected (see Appendix Figure 7.4). An AR(0) model means that for these time series a model fit without autocorrelation had the lowest BIC and the regular OLS residuals were used in change point detection.

5.2.1 Change Point Timing

Looking at the timing of the single breakpoints, the majority of breakpoint estimates throughout the globe were between 2010-2015, with the second most common being in the years of 1985-1989 (Figure 5.5). Between 1992-2006 there were no or hardly any breakpoints (Figure 5.6).

Figure 5.5: Global image of the change point timing estimates by modified CUSUM results with manual combination correction. Barren land and ice covered areas were excluded from the analysis and are marked in white, water is blue.

Within Cluster Variability Out of 280 clusters of size larger than one, 81 clusters showed the same timing estimate for all pixels within the cluster. Of the remaining 199

Figure 5.6: Change point location estimates for all significant MCUSUM pixels with manual combination correction grouped by years.

clusters larger than one pixel around 50% had a standard deviation of ≤ 2 (see Appendix Figure 7.3), so the majority of the clusters had only small within-cluster variability of time point estimates.

5.2.2 Change Point Types

For the significant pixels, change point types were derived using Mann Kendall Trend Test and linear regression coefficients. Formally the permutation procedure only allows inference on the cluster level and not on the individual pixel level. Additionally, with spatial autocorrelation in mind and the reasoning behind the STCS procedure, clusters are therein perceived as contiguous areas of similar behavior. Thus change point types were obtained for individual pixels but also for each cluster using a majority vote. Counting the pixels by types with and without the majority vote the most common class was *Stalled Greening* in both cases, followed by pixels with non-significant Trend Tests in both segments and *Browning Onset* (Figure 5.7). The reversal types *Browning to Greening* and *Greening to Browning* had only small shares in both options. Applying the majority vote several breakpoint types like *Continued Greening* and *Greening Onset* diminished considerably, *Continued Browning* vanished completely.

Within Cluster Variability Out of the 280 clusters with size larger than 1, there were 51 clusters with equal breakpoint types at each pixel. In another 55 out of the 280 clusters, the fraction of the majority class was below 50 %, showing a high variability of breakpoint types within the cluster.

Figure 5.7: Percentage of pixels among all significant pixels of a certain breakpoint type with and without within-cluster majority vote.

Short Subtrends In the most common class *Stalled Greening*, among the pixels without majority vote 97 % had their breakpoint between 2011 - 2015. Hence periods of no significant trend after the greening trend lasted between 4-8 years. As well for pixels without majority vote assigned with class *Browning Onset*, 89 % had their breakpoint between 1985-1989. Periods of no significant trend before the beginning browning trend were between 4-8 years long.

Figure 5.8: Global image of breakpoint types, original pixel results without majority vote. Barren land and ice covered areas were excluded from the analysis and are marked in white, water is blue.

Spatial Distribution For breakpoint types without the cluster-based majority vote, *Stalled Greening* was mainly present throughout west and central Africa, eastern China, and the northern edges of North America, often mixed with pixels of two non-significant segments. Larger clusters of *Browning Onset* were located in eastern Ukraine, central Russia, and in the northern part of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (Figure 5.8). For a map with the breakpoint types with majority vote see Appendix Figure 7.6. For quite a few clusters the majority vote omits the high amount non-significant trend type pixels within the cluster.

5.2.3 Comparison to Monotonic Trends

The results of the Mann Kendall Trend Test corrected with the Tippet Combining Function (section 5.1) were overlaid with the corrected MCUSUM change point detection. Around 40% of the pixels declared significant with MCUSUM and manual combination correction had also shown a significant result when testing for a monotonic test with Mann Kendall - 15025 out of 37507 significant MCUSUM pixels. Looking at change point types (without cluster majority vote) for both pixels with significant as well as non-significant Mann Kendall Test, *Stalled Greening* was the most common class (Figure 5.9). *Browning Onset* and pixels with no significant segment had a much higher share in the pixels with no

Figure 5.9: Significant MCUSUM pixel grouped by change point types with either significant or non-significant Mann Kendall monotonic trend test at the same location.

significant trend test, whereas *Continued Greening* and *Greening Onset* was more present in pixels with significant trend test. Most *Browning Onset* and *Stalled Greening* pixels showed a similar length of significant browning/greening periods. Also, the magnitude of absolute change showed no big difference in the median and in the distribution of absolute slope values for the long browning and greening periods respectively (see Appendix Figure 7.8). No pixels assigned *Continued Browning* had a significant Mann Kendall Test. On the global image, the *Stalled Greening* clusters in eastern China, west and central Africa, and northern North America were the most prominent ones with significant monotonic trend test (Figure 5.10).

Change Point Detection and Monotonic Trend

Figure 5.10: Significant MCUSUM pixels coloured in green if Mann Kendall trend test was significant at the same location, coloured in blue if not. Barren land and ice covered areas were excluded from the analysis and are marked in white, water is blue.

Chapter 6

Discussion

The present study aimed to enhance the permutation-based multiple testing correction by Cortés et al. (2020) and to demonstrate its transferability, by applying it to a change point detection in global LAI trends. A statistically robust and detailed analysis of vegetational processes is the first step in understanding the role and dependencies of vegetation within the Earth system and its response to human impacts and climate change. Multiple testing can result in uncontrolled false positive rates, even more severe with dependent data, like spatially autocorrelated environmental data, as false positives may cluster. To tackle this issue, Cortés et al. (2020) have introduced a procedure based on suprathreshold clusters. We have successfully included test statistic values into the correction method to enable the detection of smaller clusters. A main difficulty in the evaluation of the change point detection results was the small extent of pixels affected by breakpoints, probably due to the rather conservative method used. The permutation procedure offers a flexible framework to easily implement new methods. However, outcomes are highly dependent on the specific method used. Although the permutation-based multiple testing correction has shown to be more powerful than Bonferroni-related ones, it is not able to increase the power of a per se conservative method applied at the individual test level. The research questions posed in chapter 3 will be discussed in more detail now.

Question 1

Does a multiple testing correction combining STCS and maximum cluster statistic offer a more sensitive approach for detecting smaller significant clusters than STCS alone?

In present applications, the Tippett Combining Function, as well as the newly implemented

manual combination of STCS and quantile-based p-value thresholding, successfully detected additional smaller clusters compared to mere STCS. No large clusters were missed with TCF meaning no power loss compared to STCS in our analysis. The manual combination procedure inherently included large clusters. In preliminary trials using other LAI datasets and the Mann Kendall trend test, TCF did not always detect additional small clusters. As there is no ground truth data available for the LAI trends, it is hard to distinguish between low power of TCF or simply no trends present. A further demonstration of the TCF's capabilities in change point detection was not possible, due to the described restrictions. The manual combination procedure was developed to mimic a similar approach that ensures false positive control in a more powerful way than STCS alone, in which we succeeded. If applicable, TCF is however preferred because of its sound theoretical basis and its previous usage in neuroimaging Hayasaka and Nichols (2004); Poline et al. (1997). A more theoretical and robust demonstration of TCF's capabilities would require a simulation with artificial data.

In both applications, trend test, and change point detection, several clusters showed major quality issues. The influence of quality issues might be more severe in small clusters of only a few pixels. Thus it seems worthwhile to implement a minimum size threshold and/or a quality-based threshold for significant clusters in future applications to obtain more meaningful results.

Question 2

How do results of change point detection on global LAI time series differ when correcting for multiple testing?

The correction with manual combination decreased the number of significant pixels and their covered areas in comparison to the uncorrected results - around 80% remained. This is a smaller reduction of significant pixels than the TCF correction on Mann Kendall Test. However, this does not correspond to an increased power of manual combination, as we could not compare it to TCF outcome in change point detection. The clusters declared significant after correction were equally distributed in space and also in terms of cluster size compared to the remaining, then non-significant clusters, showing no obvious dependence on location or cluster size in the correction method. Whether certain cluster sizes prevail after the correction also depends on the actual breakpoints present in the data. From the design of the method itself, we would not expect a bias towards certain cluster sizes, as only the minimum p-value within a cluster is regarded in the second step of manual combination.

*Question 3***Overlaying the results of change point detection and monotonic long term trend tests - does the latter omit possible breakpoints and subtrends?**

Around 40% of the pixels with a significant breakpoint also showed a significant result applying the Mann Kendall Trend Test. This supports the assumption that looking solely at monotonic long term trends obscures breakpoints and subtrends within the observed time range. Among the pixels with significant results in both tests, the greening classes (*Stalled Greening*, *Continued Greening*, and *Greening Onset*) prevailed. It's rather obvious that pixels of *Continued Greening* also appear significant in a monotonic trend test. It might still be interesting to uncover changes in slopes since a slowdown or increase in greening intensity might point to changes in ecological drivers or land management strategies. For the pixels of class *Continued Greening* slope differences had a median of -0.05 (see Appendix Figure 7.8). Thus more than half of these time series showed a decreased greening rate in the second segment. For the other greening classes that showed significant Mann Kendall Tests, in most of the pixels the greening periods were longer than 28 years, spanning over 75% of the analyzed time span. As with the *Continued Greening*, it isn't surprising either that Mann Kendall assumes a monotonic trend in these cases. However as mentioned previously, short periods of no trend followed or preceded by long greening periods might still be of ecological interest. Remarkably for *Browning Onset* with similarly short non-significant segments like *Stalled Greening*, coincidence with significant monotonic trend test was much lower. Absolute slope values were also similar among the two types, the remaining difference was, that the non-significant period was either at the beginning or the end of the time series. On the one hand, this demonstrates how change point detection can deliver more complex information on vegetation processes. On the other hand, a more detailed look into the reasons for this issue would be necessary, to assure that monotonic trend analysis does not underestimate browning systematically. The reversal type *Greening to Browning* was equally represented in the group of significant and non-significant Mann Kendall Test. Thus we cannot infer that opposing trends necessarily cancel each other out and thereby result in a non-significant monotonic trend test. This heavily depends on the timing of trend reversal within the time series though.

*Question 4***Which global image regarding occurrence and types of breakpoints is presented by the corrected results compared to previous studies?**

Comparison with other studies is usually limited to a certain extent since other methods

were used and results were evaluated differently. However there are two global studies on vegetation change point detection, as presented in section 2.1.3, that also looked for a single breakpoint using the GIMMS 3g NDVI dataset, the source of the BU LAI dataset (De Jong et al., 2013; Pan et al., 2018).

As suspected through preliminary simulation with random data, MCUSUM is rather conservative. Looking at own trials with other change point detection methods and comparing the uncorrected results with those of the other global breakpoint studies, the global area declared to contain a breakpoint was considerably smaller (De Jong et al., 2013; Pan et al., 2018). De Jong et al. (2013) had pixels with change points all over the globe including the whole of Australia, the horn of Africa, southern parts of Africa, South America, and North America among others. They had no change points in eastern China where MCUSUM results showed a major clustering and the northern higher latitudes were excluded from the analysis. Also in the study by Pan et al. (2018), all three methods applied yielded significant breakpoints all over the earth's land surface. Regarding the timing of breakpoints, in the analysis by De Jong et al. (2013) the peak of change points was between 2003-2008 (the dataset ranged from 1981-2011). The frequency of breakpoints increased with the years and they had rather low frequencies in the early 1980s. Two methods by Pan et al. (2018) showed a peak frequency in 2006, for all other time points the distribution was rather equal. Our results differ profoundly. Although we have high occurrences of breakpoints at the end of the time series like De Jong et al. (2013), rates are equally high in the early 1980s and the lack of breakpoints between 1990-2010 contradicts the results of both other studies. The plausibility of our breakpoint timing estimates will be discussed later on.

De Jong et al. (2013); Pan et al. (2018) have both derived a classification scheme for breakpoint types that differs slightly from the present one. De Jong et al. (2013) have not applied further significance testing to the slopes. Segments with slopes smaller than 0.25 % per year were declared as stable segments. Pan et al. (2018) did include significance tests but only time series with two significant segments were assigned a breakpoint type. Concurrent with our results, both studies had quite an amount of non-significant or stable time series segments. Pan et al. (2018) showed even higher numbers than in the present results, which is explicable by their characterization design. Apart from the stable time series greening types prevailed in all studies, including the present one. Reversal types especially *Greening to Browning* were more frequent in both Pan et al. (2018) and De Jong et al. (2013) than in our MCUSUM results. In Pan et al. (2018) *Greening to Browning* was even the second to third most common class after non-significant segments. In the

regions where our breakpoint characterization yielded *Stalled Greening*, Pan et al. (2018) have mostly identified *Greening to Greening* / *Continued Greening*.

De Jong et al. (2013) and Pan et al. (2018) have disagreed on the situation in the northern high latitude. De Jong et al. (2013) had excluded tundra and boreal forests from the analysis because of quality issues and because of a previous study they had conducted, which showed no major effects of discontinuities in the region. Pan et al. (2018) argue, that based on their results browning has expanded largely in the last decades in the northern high latitudes and omitting them would underestimate the increase in global browning trends. Our change point detection found mainly *Stalled Greening* in northern North America as well as northern Russia, wherein the latter there was also some *Browning Onset* and *Greening to Browning* present. However, these latitudes are indeed one of the most affected by quality issues (see Figure 4.1) and it's unclear to what extent the detection of breakpoints is influenced by this type of data alteration. Although *Browning Onset* was the third most common class in our analysis, this does not necessarily support Pan et al. (2018)'s assumption of underestimated expansion of browning. The area covered by *Browning Onset* is rather small on a global level, also due to the possibly conservative MCUSUM. Furthermore, most of the *Browning Onset* pixels have their breakpoints in the first years of the time series, so browning is rather a long term trend in these areas.

Similar to the disagreements on northern higher latitudes the tropical forests are known to have substantial uncertainties in NDVI values and LAI estimates. This is rooted in saturation effects of the indices as well as cloud contamination (Chen et al., 2019a; Piao et al., 2019; Jiang et al., 2017). De Jong et al. (2012) argued that abrupt changes might still be detectable however results should be interpreted with care. In our analysis, this included clusters in western and central Africa as well as clusters scattered around Brazil. The regions were dominated by *Stalled Greening* combined with a fair amount of *Browning Onset* and *Greening to Browning* pixels. This is somewhat similar to the distribution of change point types in the tropical forests in Pan et al. (2018)'s results, which seem to be dominated by *Greening to Greening* and *Greening to Browning*. De Jong et al. (2013) had fewer pixels with change points in the region, among those greening types prevailed, mixed with some *Greening to Browning*.

Question 5

Is the permutation-based procedure for multiple testing correction by Cortés et al. (2020) easily transferable to another environmental use case?

The code by Cortés et al. (2020) is meant as a flexible framework that allows using it

with any other hypothesis testing method. From the coding perspective, this goal is met. In trials throughout the research process, also other methods apart from MCUSUM have been successfully implemented into the permutation correction. The main requirement of a method is that it provides either p-values or it is possible to derive p-values or test statistic thresholds¹. This is necessary to define suprathreshold clusters. The option for the minimum p-value approach was implemented for MCUSUM. For other test statistics that do not come from a normal or a t-distribution the user has to insert the respective transformation or test statistic thresholds for their method into Cortés et al. (2020)'s code. Apart from the technical details on code modification, the usefulness of the permutation procedure is highly dependent on the chosen testing method. In the current use case, the two major constraints applying the correction procedure were computing time and quasi discrete p-values. The computing time of MCUSUM could be reduced to about 1 second per function call and the testing was parallelized within permuted images. Still testing nearly 2 million pixels in each permuted image was not feasible for several hundred permutations. In other settings, computational limitations might matter less, for example, applications with a smaller number of testing locations like a smaller study area or climatic station data. Also, a more powerful and less frequently used high performance cluster can alleviate computational constraints. Nevertheless, as in other computationally intensive analyses, the computational effort should be traded off with the expected quality and explanatory power of the results. As seen with MCUSUM, the multiple testing correction is not able to increase the power of a rather conservative method.

When using combined approaches of cluster size and test statistic values like TCF and our manual combination, results are more useful with continuous test statistic values. The quasi discrete p-values resulting from the bootstrapping in MCUSUM undermined the idea of deriving an empirical maximum statistic/minimum p-value distribution. It is unclear how to obtain corrected p-values from a distribution with many values being exactly equal. The resulting p-values would be fairly arbitrary.

Further Limitations

Beyond the limitations that arose in answering the research questions, we faced further challenges in the research process. The remaining part of the discussion will cover additional constraints in interpreting the results and directions for future research.

Plausibility of Change Point Estimates Surprisingly the detected change points were mainly located at the borders of the time series. Lyubchich et al. (2020) found that in

¹For further theoretical requirements see section 2.2.3 and Cortés et al. (2020).

modified CUSUM power decreases the further away change points are located from the center of the time series. The observed breakpoints at the edges could be of exceptional magnitude, however in an experimental power simulation using time series with artificially introduced breakpoints, we could not observe a power increase in the center for our MCUSUM modification (see Appendix Figure 7.7). For changes in mean or intercept the power even decreased when breakpoints were located in the middle of the time series. For changes in slope, which MCUSUM is aimed at, the method had more or less constant power and showed no distinct peak in the middle. This behavior could be due to the adjustments made to the method, like the trimming of the combinations. This assumption still lacks a theoretical foundation though and should be investigated more thoroughly before applying our adaptation of MCUSUM in other use cases.

Apart from the agglomeration of change points at the borders, there was an additional uncertainty about the change point location estimates. In the years 1985 and 2011/2012 there was a high number of change points and these years coincide with platform changes of the NOAA AVHRR system (Table 4.2). Although Tian et al. (2015) have found the highest temporal consistency in GIMMS 3g NDVI compared to other datasets and De Jong et al. (2012, 2011) only reported few sensor changes concurring with periods of elevated break point numbers, this coincidence cannot be disregarded. Especially combined with the suspected lower power of MCUSUM in the middle section and overall conservativeness of the method the origin of the detected breakpoints should be interpreted with care. In the scope of this analysis, it was not possible to link vegetation change with different drivers to differentiate between artificial and ecological shifts. Depending on the particular change point detection method it might also be an idea to introduce a certain bias that makes the detection of a change point in temporal proximity to platform or sensor changes less probable. The extent to which other breakpoint timings are favored would be somewhat arbitrary though.

Temporal Autocorrelation An assumption made for the permutation-based correction procedure is the exchangeability of the data. Temporal autocorrelation though diminishes exchangeability. By yearly aggregation of LAI values, the effect of seasonal correlations could be impaired. However to account for remaining temporal autocorrelation the integrated model selection approach of MCUSUM was used, instead of a preliminary decorrelation shown to be challenging in change point detection. Hence possible temporal autocorrelation structures were not considered before permuting the images but afterwards within the testing procedure. Strictly speaking, the possible autocorrelation in yearly aggregates then somewhat degraded exchangeability. In the present analysis, the majority

of the pixels were fitted with an AR(0) model, returning the best model fit without any temporal autocorrelation. Thus we assume, that the violation of the exchangeability assumption did not influence the results strongly. The flexible framework of MCUSUM using a model selection for autoregressive order is highly advantageous in the analysis remote sensing data, since neither manual evaluation of single time series is necessary, nor a generalized assumption on autocorrelation structure of all pixels. The widely used time series decomposition methods deal with temporal autocorrelation by fitting seasonal models, nonetheless, this impedes applying the powerful permutation-based multiple testing correction.

Reduced Number of Permutations As already mentioned the major compromise of MCUSUM is its computing time. The bootstrap approach allows avoiding asymptotic assumptions, however, prolongs the computation. The same applies to the comparison of various combinations, which provides a flexible analysis tool with the downside of high computational cost. In the original implementation by Lyubchich et al. (2020) the modified CUSUM is rather suited for the analysis of a handful of time series or analysis of gridded environmental data that does not involve permutations. Computing time coupled with server capacities was the main factor that the number of bootstraps and permutations had to be reduced and thus correction with TCF was no longer useful. A higher number of permutations probably hadn't changed the global image completely, however, due to the cluster-based approach, with a change in thresholds, it's whole clusters that can appear/disappear and not only scattered singular pixels. Lyubchich et al. (2020) propose to derive possible change point locations through preliminary tests. Depending on the complexity of the tests this might be an option for gridded data to avoid comparing a large number of possible locations.

Ecological Interpretation of Results As change point detection studies have challenged the image of a greening world and have proposed that browning processes are underestimated (Pan et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2011), *Stalled Greening*, *Browning Onset* and *Greening to Browning* reversal are probably the most interesting classes as they might be a sign of a slow down or reversal of greening trends. *Stalled Greening* pixels are indeed the most frequent ones in our analysis. However, since they are mainly located in regions strongly affected by quality issues (northern higher latitudes and tropical forests), have only short segments of non-greening and breakpoints in many cases coincide with a platform change of the NOAA satellites, there is not enough evidence to claim sustained ecological shifts. From an ecological perspective, short term trends or short periods of stable behavior of 4-7 years are not per se irrelevant but have to be interpreted carefully.

Vegetation productivity can be influenced by cyclical events, like El Niño-Southern Oscillation and abrupt events like volcanic eruptions or years with temperature anomalies. These events however do not necessarily cause a change in gradual long term greening and browning processes (De Jong et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2014). Especially for the *Stalled Greening* pixels, where stable periods occur at the end of the time series and no further data is available, it is hard to distinguish between an anomalous stalling or the onset of a different regime. Linking the LAI changes with possible drivers would allow a more sound interpretation. Additionally, to avoid misinterpreting periods of cyclical phenomena, the minimum segment length could also be prolonged. In the current analysis, it was set to 4 years, similar to other studies (Forkel et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2014; De Jong et al., 2013). The minimum segment length determines possible change point locations and thereby also influences the results of subtrends (Chen et al., 2014).

When applying the cluster-based correction procedure, within-cluster variability of breakpoint timing estimates and breakpoint types poses a challenge. The idea of the cluster-based approach is to regard clusters as areas of similar behavior and formally only allows inference on the cluster as a whole. However, adjacent significant pixels do not necessarily correspond to a more or less homogeneous area in terms of ecological conditions. The majority vote as applied here has shown to omit high variability and thus resulted in a loss of details. Nonetheless, for breakpoint timing estimates and breakpoint types, it is not possible or little meaningful to derive a different summary statistic than mode.

Last but not least the conservative MCUSUM only yielded significant breakpoints for a small amount of the earth's land surface scattered around the world in small to medium-sized clusters. This makes the evaluation of vegetational shifts in larger regions challenging.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

Global vegetation trends have been studied thoroughly using remote sensing based indices resulting in the image of a greening world. Change point detection aims at providing more detailed knowledge of vegetational processes than monotonic trend analysis can offer. Long term trends might be composed of possibly opposing subtrends or relatively stable periods. Cortés et al. (2020) have introduced a permutation-based procedure to correct for multiple testing, a possibly severe though overlooked issue in statistical analysis of gridded environmental data. The main goal of this study was to refine their procedure and apply it to a further use case and thereby provide statistically more robust results of global vegetational breakpoints. The focus was rather on methodological challenges than on an in-depth ecological interpretation of the results.

We successfully detected smaller significant clusters by including test statistic values in the cluster-based correction procedure. The new combined approaches thus propose themselves as an even more powerful correction method than the STCS, merely based on cluster size. Applying the correction to change point detection results the number of significant pixels was reduced as expected, though to a rather small amount. Although being fairly conservative, the MCUSUM detected significant breakpoints in 2.2% of the analyzed earth land surface. Other global change point detection studies have shown considerably larger areas affected by shifts and subtrends, even compared to our uncorrected results. Breakpoint types involving greening processes prevailed in our studies as well as in the compared ones. Reversal types were less frequent in the current analysis. Although *Stalled Greening* was the most widely spread breakpoint type and more than half of *Continued Greening* pixels showed a decrease in slope in the second segment, there is not enough evidence to claim a slow down of global greening or increased browning rate, as only a minor share

of the earth surface was covered and breakpoint estimates showed various uncertainties. Comparing the results to a monotonic trend analysis with Mann Kendall Test, 40% of the pixels affected by breakpoints also showed significant monotonic trends. This suggests that a monotonic trend analysis firstly misses pixels with trends spanning only parts of the time series, as seen with pixels of type *Browning Onset* that were not recognized by Mann Kendall trend test, although they included up to 33 years of browning. Secondly, in significant monotonic trends subtrends may be masked by the generalization.

From a technical perspective, the application of the multiple testing correction implemented by Cortés et al. (2020) to another use case was straightforward. The structure of the procedure offers a flexible framework with low requirements for the new testing method. Nevertheless, the permutations can be quite computationally expensive, depending on the size of the dataset and the computing time of the chosen test. Server capacities should also be included in considerations on feasibility and balancing of computing time against expected quality of results. Last but not least, the permutation-based correction, though powerful, cannot extract more information than the chosen testing method does, neither is it able to increase the power of a per se conservative method.

For a more generic proof of the newly developed correction procedure, a simulation study with artificial data would be useful. Anyhow, the detection of smaller clusters is always dependent on the current dataset and whether small clusters with high test statistic values exist. The modified CUSUM for change point detection has beneficial theoretical properties like the model selection for autoregressive order. However, we discovered a stagnancy or even decrease of power in our modified version for change points in the middle of the time series, which is oppositional to the method characteristics as described by Lyubchich et al. (2020). A more elaborated simulation and a theoretical discussion on the validity of the modifications would be necessary to investigate this issue more profoundly. Due to this behavior of MCUSUM and a coincidence of the years with high breakpoint frequency with platform changes of the NOAA satellite system, the plausibility of our breakpoint timing estimates is questionable and results should be interpreted cautiously. Furthermore, the diminished quality of LAI estimates especially in tropical forests and in the northern latitudes is still an unsolved issue. An additional quality-based threshold in significance testing could ensure more reliable identification of meaningful significant clusters.

We have demonstrated the transferability of the permutation-based correction that ensures a robust control of false positives in a multiple testing setting and the presence of spatial autocorrelation. The new combination of cluster size and test statistic intensity outperformed the merely cluster-based approach and conventional Bonferroni-related ap-

proaches. Publishing the code by Cortés et al. (2020) with the presented modifications will hopefully increase the visibility of this powerful correction approach in the remote sensing community and related environmental sciences where multiple testing is often encountered. In a general ecological interpretation, it must be kept in mind when using LAI data, that an increase in vegetation productivity does not necessarily mean an increase in biodiversity or an ecologically valuable vegetation cover. The assessment of changes in vegetation productivity can only be the first step, followed by a more detailed examination of possible drivers to gain a more thorough understanding of the interdependencies and sources of short and long term changes and trends. Although effects of global climate change like prolonged growing season and CO₂ fertilization have bolstered greening in many regions of the world, this process might saturate if critical thresholds are crossed (Piao et al., 2014, 2019; Vickers et al., 2016). Land management strategies also have major impacts on the composition of vegetation cover and its ecological value. Thus allowing for subtrends and trend reversals within the study period can add important details in the study of vegetation productivity trends.

Appendix

Table 7.1: False positive rates for different change point detection methods at $\alpha = 0.05$. Derived from simulated random normally distributed time series with 38 observations without change points, 1000 repetitions each.

Method and Reference	False Positive Rate
Wild Binary Segmentation (Fryzlewicz, 2014), <i>wbsts</i> package, time series length 400, error for shorter time series	0.053
Recursive CUSUM (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package	0.038
OLS CUSUM (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package	0
Score CUSUM (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package	0.017
Recursive MOSUM (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package, value range for different window sizes	0-0.038
OLS MOSUM (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package, value range for different window sizes	0-0.039
Recursive Estimates (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package	0.04
F-Statistics (Zeileis et al., 2003), <i>strucchange</i> package, value range for different summary statistics	0.06-0.1
At-most-one-change Mean (Killick et al., 2012), <i>changeoint</i> package	0
At-most-one-change Variance (Killick et al., 2012), <i>changeoint</i> package	0.012
At-most-one-change Mean and Variance (Killick et al., 2012), <i>changeoint</i> package	1
Pettitt Test (Pettitt, 1979), <i>trend</i> package	0.027
Modified CUSUM (Lyubchich et al., 2020), <i>funtimes</i> package	0

Table 7.2: Cluster-size-dependent thresholds for minimum p-value of a cluster, derived from manual combination procedure.

Cluster Size	P-value Threshold
1	0.028
2-5	0.012
6-10	0.004
11-20	0.002
21-50	0.002
51-100	0.002
101-200	0.002
201-300	0.002
301-400	0.006
401-500	0.002
501-600	0.002
601-700	0.0026
701-800	0.002
801-900	0.002
>900	0.002

Figure 7.1: Clusters declared significant in modified CUSUM by manual combination counted by size.

Figure 7.2: Comparison of size distribution of clusters declared significant in modified CUSUM by manual combination (top) and uncorrected significant cluster of plain MCUSUM (bottom).

Figure 7.3: Within Cluster Standard Deviation of Change point timing estimates for significant MCUSUM clusters with manual combination correction excluding clusters of size one and clusters with equal estimates at each pixel.

Figure 7.4: Frequencies of Autoregressive Orders chosen in modified CUSUM for all significant pixels of manual combination.

Figure 7.5: Size of significant clusters of MCUSUM and manual combination correction with their median value of percentage of time points with quality issues. The size of the points corresponds to the interquartile range (IQR) within the cluster.

Modified CUSUM Breakpoint Types

Figure 7.6: Global image of breakpoint types, aggregated cluster-wise with a majority vote. Barren land and ice covered areas were excluded from the analysis and are marked in white, water is blue.

Figure 7.7: Power simulations of modified CUSUM with different types of change (see Figure 2.1) at alternating change point locations. At each time point 50 repetitions were performed with a different randomly generated artificial time series each. Gaps in the curve of mean change are due to violations of the stationarity assumption of MCUSUM.

Figure 7.8: Distribution of slope magnitudes and slope differences for all pixels assigned with the respective breakpoint type. For *Continued Greening* pixels, first boxplot on the left, the slope value of the second segment was subtracted from the the slope value of the first segment. For *Stalled Greening* and *Browning Onset* the slope value of the one significant segment was used.

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Declaration of Originality

I confirm that this master's thesis is my own work and that I have not sought or used inadmissible help of third parties to produce this work and that I have clearly referenced all sources used in the work. All passage taken from a source, whether verbatim or in substance, have been indicated as such. This work has not yet been submitted to another examination institution - neither in Germany nor outside Germany – neither in the same nor in a similar way and has not yet been published.

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Veronika Grupp